

**AN ANALYTICAL STUDY OF PAT MARTINO'S SOLO LINES
FROM SELECTED SIX COMPOSITIONS**

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**A THEMATIC PAPER SUBMITTED IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT
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Thematic Paper
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ABSTRACT

This research explored Pat Martino's improvisational techniques in depth by analysing six works that represent different periods of his career. The selected pieces include "Just Friends," "Joyous Lake," "Turnpike," "Think Tank," "Lean Year," and "Full House." Each represents a different stage of his musical evolution. Transcriptions of these works serve as the primary source for this examination of Martino's unique approach to jazz guitar improvisation.

This study employed detailed transcription and analysis to investigate Martino's improvisational style from four key perspectives: melodic construction, rhythm, harmonics, and special techniques. Analyses of each of these revealed how Martino used minor substitutions, chromatic embellishments, rhythmic displacements, and extraordinary left- and right-hand guitar techniques to create his distinct sound. In this research, practical exercises were further developed based on these improvisational techniques. These exercises will offer musicians concrete methods to incorporate Martino's approaches into their practice routines. Additionally, this aims to bridge the gap between theoretical understanding and practical application, enhancing the improvisational skills and artistic expression of jazz musicians.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE THEMATIC PAPER

The implications of this thematic paper extend to both practical performance and jazz education. The analysis of Pat Martino's improvisational style across different phases of his career will deepen jazz musicians' understanding of how advanced theoretical concepts translate into practical improvisation. The detailed breakdown of

Martino's melodic construction and of his rhythmic, harmonic, and special techniques will offer concrete ways for musicians to enhance their improvisational language.

For educators, the exercises designed from these techniques will serve as valuable resources, enabling the integration of Martino's methods into teaching materials. These exercises bridge the gap between theoretical analysis and practical implementation. These activities will help students develop their own improvisational skills while staying rooted in foundational jazz tradition. The insights gained from this study not only contribute to a richer understanding of Martino's legacy but also inspire future musicians to push the boundaries of jazz improvisation.

KEYWORDS: PAT MARTINO / JAZZ GUITAR / IMPROVISATION /
PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

133 pages

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CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background Information

Pat Martino is regarded as one of the most innovative guitarists in modern jazz, known for his unique approach to linear improvisation. His musical development was deeply influenced by the bebop and hard bop traditions, while also incorporating concepts from geometry, the alphabet, and Taoist hexagrams. These elements gave his improvisational style a high degree of logic and coherence. Early on, Martino was influenced by guitar legends such as Johnny Smith, Les Paul and Wes Montgomery, and he began exploring the relationships between melodic lines and harmonic structures at a young age. His collaborations with musicians like Willis Jackson and Brother Jack McDuff helped establish his foundation in hard bop and soul jazz, showcasing his creativity within these styles.¹

Following surgery for a brain aneurysm surgery in 1980, Martino had to relearn how to play the guitar, which deepened his understanding of musical structure and melody. After his recovery, his playing style became more focused on emotional and melodic expression, while still maintaining technical precision. This evolution also reflected his profound reflections on music. Martino made significant contributions to music education by combining mathematical and geometric principles with improvisation, particularly through his use of clock-like geometric diagrams to visualize and understand intervals, chords, and scales. This method gave students a new way to understand music, focusing on linear minor-scale thinking in improvisation rather than learning every mode individually. It also helped address some of the challenges associated with the vast number of modes in guitar playing.²

¹ Dave Frank, "Dave Frank Jazz Master Class - An Evening with Pat Martino," YouTube video, September 6, 2016, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PY74aRTMmbA&t=2509s>.

² Open Road, directed by Pat Martino (Vestapol, 2014), DVD, 2 hr.

This study provides an in-depth analysis of Martino's improvisational style and offers musicians practical methods for incorporating these techniques into their own performances. By understanding Martino's musical structures, musicians can enhance their improvisational skills and benefit from his creative insights in their artistic expression.

1.2 Objectives

1.2.1 To conduct an in-depth analysis of Pat Martino's improvised solos in six classic pieces.

1.2.2 To design practical exercises to help musicians apply Pat Martino's theories and techniques in their playing.

1.3 Scope of the Study

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of Pat Martino's improvisational playing style, focusing on the theoretical foundations and techniques of soloing in works from various stages of his career. However, while Pat Martino's comping techniques hold significant research value, this study primarily focuses on his solo lines. This approach will allow for a thorough understanding of the solo stylistic characteristics that define each period of his musical evolution. The research will employ rigorous musical analysis, including detailed guitar solo transcriptions of his performances, to ensure an in-depth examination of his artistry. Six representative works covering different phases of Martino's career have been selected for this analysis, as seen in the following table:

Table 1.1 Details of the Six Classic Pieces³

³ Pat Martino, "Discography," *Pat Martino Official Website*, accessed <https://www.patmartino.com/>.

Titles	Style	Recording Date	Record labels	Released Year	Credits	Album
“Just Friends”	Hard Bop	May1, 1967	Prestige	1967	Guitar: Pat Martino, Organ: Trudy Pitts, Flute: Danny Turner, Drums: Mitch Fine, Congas: Abdu Johnson	<i>El Hombre (1967)</i>
“Joyous Lake”	Jazz Fusion	1976	Warner Bros	1977	Guitar: Pat Martino, Electric Piano: Delmar Brown, Bass: Kenwood Dennard, Drums: Allen Schwartzberg	<i>Joyous Lake (1977)</i>
“Turnpike”	Hard Bop	November 1995	N/A	N/A	Guitar: Pat Martino, Piano: James Ridl, Bass: Steve Beskron, Drums: Scott Robinson	<i>Live at The Knitting Factory, NYC</i>
“Think Tank”	Post-Bop	2003	Blue Note Records	2003	Guitar: Pat Martino, Bass: Christian McBride, Piano: Gonzalo Rubalcaba, Drums: Lewis Nash	<i>Think Tank</i>
“Lean Years”	Hard Bop	2009	HighNote Records	2011	Guitar: Pat Martino, Organ: Tony Monaco, Drums: Jeff “Tain” Watts, Saxophone: Eric Alexander	<i>Undeniable: Live at Blues Alley</i>

“Full House”	Hard Bop	2014	N/A	N/A	Guitar: Pat Martino, Organ: Pat Bianchi, Drums: Carmen Intorre, Live Trio Performance at Bielska Zadymka Jazzowa	<i>Pat Martino Trio, Bielska Zadymka Jazzowa</i>
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The analysis in this study is presented in four sections focusing on the themes detailed below:

Melodic Construction Analysis: This section will explore Martino’s approach to melodic construction, particularly his use of sequences, intervallic transformations, rhythmic transformation, pivot tone, octave displacement, passing tones, neighbor tones, indirect resolution, chromatic approach, double chromatic approach and enclosure. These techniques are crucial for understanding Martino’s linear thinking and his innovative approach to melodic development.

Rhythmic Analysis: The study will examine Martino’s rhythmic approach, with particular attention to rhythmic anticipation, metric displacement, and the variations of his signature rhythmic patterns.

Harmonic Analysis: This section will delve into Martino’s melody in different harmonic approach across different periods of his work, specifically focusing on his use of minor substitution materials, the implied upper structures hidden within his phrases, and his application of digital patterns.

Special Techniques Analysis: This section will review key guitar techniques, including double-stops, slide combined with the 3-against-4 technique, open strings, string bending combined with the 3-against-4 technique, economy picking, string bends, stairway chromaticism, and octave chromatic displacement.

The purpose of this study is not to provide an exhaustive biography of Pat Martino or cover all aspects of his career but to summarize Martino’s improvisational techniques and examine his theoretical system. The exercises in the Martino style are intended to help musicians better integrate these elements into their own playing.

1.4 Expectations

This paper aims to provide readers with a deep understanding of Pat Martino's improvisational style and theoretical framework through an in-depth analysis of six representative pieces. By transcribing and analyzing these improvisations, the study offers both theoretical insights and practical resources that can be effectively applied by musicians in their performances.

Another important objective of this research is to provide valuable educational resources for jazz enthusiasts and music educators. The exercises and application guidelines developed in this study can serve as practical tools for educators, assisting students in comprehending and applying Martino's theories and methods.

In particular, this study seeks to bridge the gap between theory and practice by offering concrete methods that musicians can adopt in their practice routines. The practical exercises are intended to aid performers in mastering Martino's technical and theoretical approaches, and educators can incorporate these exercises into teaching materials for jazz improvisation courses. This holistic approach caters to the diverse needs of jazz musicians, enthusiasts, and educators alike, fostering a deeper understanding of Martino's improvisational mastery.

CHAPTER II

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Pat Martino's Biography

Pat Martino was born as Pat Azzara on August 25, 1944, in Philadelphia.⁴ Began his remarkable journey with the guitar at the age of three when he discovered a Gibson guitar hidden under his parents' bed. Despite being forbidden from entering the room, Martino's curiosity drove him to pluck the strings, cutting his fingers in the process. He then used his blood to draw on the walls, marking his first interaction with the instrument that would shape his life. When Martino was twelve, his father purchased him his first guitar from a pawn shop, an act that symbolized the beginning of Martino's musical journey. This moment formed what Martino would later describe as a "full circle," signifying the profound connection he felt toward the guitar. As his passion grew, his father later gifted him a gold-colored Les Paul, solidifying Martino's commitment to his craft and paving the way for his illustrious career.⁵

Between the ages of 11 and 12, Martino's father, Carmen "Mickey" Azzara, took him to see Mary Ford and Les Paul perform, marking Martino's first encounter with Les Paul. This introduction blossomed into a close friendship that significantly influenced Martino's artistic development.⁵ When Martino was 13, his father once again introduced him to a pivotal figure in jazz guitar: Wes Montgomery.⁶ This meeting sparked a deep connection between the two musicians that lasted until Montgomery's passing in 1968.⁶ As a teenager, Martino studied for four months under Dennis Sandole, where he encountered Sandole's student, John Coltrane. Their relationship quickly grew

⁴ *Martino Unstrung: A Brain Mystery*, directed by George Kanzler (Sixteen Films, 2008), 00:00:00–20:00:00.

⁵ Bob Miles, "Pat Martino - Part 1 of 4 with Bob Miles," *YouTube video*, 2016, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5RlqM9lKFwo>.

⁶ Christian McBride, "Pat Martino - Full Interview with Christian McBride," *YouTube video*, 2021, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oZLtHd01ePA>.

beyond mentorship; Coltrane treated Martino as a close protégé, fostering a bond that resembled that of father and son.⁷

At the age of 15, Martino dropped out of high school, moved to Harlem, and seized the opportunity to join Lloyd Price's band, becoming a full member by the age of 16. At 18, he established himself as a hard-bop guitarist through collaborations with saxophonist Willis Jackson and organist Jack McDuff. In 1963, Martino spent an entire night at Wells Chicken and Waffles, a restaurant in Harlem, in the company of fellow guitarists Wes Montgomery, Les Paul, Grant Green, and George Benson, until sunrise. They shared guitar techniques and forged deep friendships.⁸

In the fall of 1964, Martino met his first wife and began collaborations with Donald Byrd, Billy James, Eric Kloss, and Jack McDuff. In 1967, he established his reputation with his debut album as a bandleader, *El Hombre*. This was followed by a number of classic works, including the stylistically diverse jazz albums *East*, *Joyous Lake*, and *Baiyina*. In the late 1970s, Martino's health took a drastic turn. During his time at the Guitar Institute of Technology, he experienced severe headaches and was misdiagnosed with a psychiatric condition, for which he underwent shock therapy.⁹

In 1980, his condition deteriorated further, such that he was given only two hours to live. He survived after two surgeries to treat brain aneurysms, but woke up having lost much of his memory, including memories of his family, friends, and even his identity as a guitarist.¹⁰ Despite this, Martino was determined to relearn the guitar. With encouragement from his father and the assistance of his student, John Mulhearn, he regained his musical ability by listening to his early recordings, ultimately making a successful comeback in 1987 with the album *The Return*.¹¹

In 1996, Martino met his second wife, Aya, in Tokyo, and they married on February 7, 1997, in Philadelphia. With Aya's support, Martino achieved further recovered both physically and mentally. He continued to thrive in the jazz world, cementing his historical standing while demonstrating his passion and perseverance in

⁷ Pat Martino and Bill Milkowski, *Here and Now!: The Autobiography of Pat Martino*, Illustrated ed. (Backbeat Books, 2011), 21–28.

⁸ Martino and Milkowski, *Here and Now!*, 33–35.

⁹ Martino and Milkowski, *Here and Now!*, 36–71.

¹⁰ Christian McBride, "Pat Martino - Full Interview with Christian McBride," *YouTube video*, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oZLtHd01ePA>.

¹¹ Pat Martino, "Biography," *Pat Martino Official Website*, <https://www.patmartino.com/biography.php>

music.¹² As jazz guitarist Emily Remler remarked, “I haven’t heard a guitar player of any real note that has not copied some of his stuff and been influenced by him in the last twenty years.”¹³ In a 2021 Facebook post, Lage Lund referred to Pat Martino as the “Bruce Lee” of the jazz world.¹⁴

Martino’s contributions to jazz went beyond technical skills; he emphasized the emotional and spiritual value of music, advocating for its universality and transcendence. In his own words, “True music, like all true art, is an experience to be shared, not judged. Praise can’t make it better, just as blame can’t make it worse.”¹³

Later in his career, Martino actively shared his performance experiences through university masterclasses, book publications, online courses, and interviews. He provided a wealth of performance materials and exceptional guitar techniques. While scales, arpeggios, and theory remained at the core of guitar teachings, Martino’s pedagogical approach offered a unique perspective on understanding jazz guitar. He emphasized linear improvisation, which differed from the traditional vertical approach, and integrated mathematical and geometrical concepts, providing musicians with a novel way to understand music theory. Embracing his style not only improved musicians’ improvisational skills for jazz standards but also helped them gain a deeper appreciation of their instrument’s potential.

Martino’s career was tragically cut short when he passed away on November 1, 2021, due to complications from lung disease.¹⁵ However, his legacy endures through his recordings, teachings, and the profound influence he continues to exert on generations of musicians.

2.2 A Survey of Stylistic Influences on Pat Martino’s Performance

¹² Martino and Milkowski, *Here and Now!*, 91-96.

¹³ Pat Martino, *Open Road*.

¹⁴ Lage Lund, “RIP Pat Martino, Unquestionably One of the Greatest Guitarists of All Time,” Facebook, 2021, <https://www.facebook.com/100000566233949/posts/pfbid0FrBAQPFSvsC3Eu5gunLUXeoRbXAUiyDNzyfvPjEmxAKJBKIdTHBVe7a9rMUeDDP6l/?mibextid=cr9u03>.

¹⁵ Pat Martino, “News,” *Pat Martino Official Website*, <https://www.patmartino.com/>.

In this section, I examine the key influences on Pat Martino's unique playing style, drawing insights from three sources in which he articulates his personal perspective. The fourth source, Tony Baruso's *Linear Expressions*, provides an external viewpoint, offering a detailed exploration of Martino's performance and conceptual approach during the late 1970s. Together, these perspectives present a comprehensive historical foundation for understanding the development of Martino's distinctive style.

2.2.1 J.W. Pepper's "Pat Martino: Here and Now"

In an interview conducted by J. W. Pepper, Pat Martino reflects on his musical career, personal challenges, and philosophical approach to music. He elaborates on his understanding of the concept of "second nature," a state achieved through intense focus and repeated practice, where musical technique and artistry become an instinctive part of the musician. Martino emphasizes that music is not merely about technical prowess but also a response to the environment, emotions, and culture. He highlights how the interaction between performer and audience, in conjunction with the overall atmosphere, deeply impacts musical expression. Martino further recounts his near-death experience from a brain aneurysm and his subsequent recovery. Through sheer determination and passion for music, he relearned guitar playing, further enhancing his artistic expression. He stresses that this recovery period profoundly influenced his pursuit of music, leading him to appreciate the present moment and the fluidity of life.

Additionally, Martino discusses his exploration of various musical styles, ranging from Latin jazz to traditional hard bop, underscoring his commitment to musical diversity. He points out that collaborating with different musicians and engaging with various musical forms enriched his experience and helped shape his distinctive playing style. Moreover, Martino critiques modern music education, particularly students' over-reliance on transcription. While transcription can be a useful tool, he argues that many students neglect the emotional and contextual elements behind the music. Martino stresses that music is created not only by the performer but also by the surrounding environment, including the audience and all aspects of the performance setting. Lastly, Martino reflects on the differences between today's music scene and his earlier years. He believes that while times have changed, these changes are not negative but rather part of music's natural evolution. He observes that each era has its own unique energy

and musical expression, and the key for musicians is to find their own voice within the present moment.¹⁶

2.2.2 Pat Martino and Bill Milkowski's Here and Now!: The Autobiography of Pat Martino

In *Here and Now!: The Autobiography of Pat Martino*, co-authored by Pat Martino and Bill Milkowski, Martino offers a comprehensive account of his musical development and career. The autobiography traces Martino's early musical path under the influence of his father, his teenage collaborations and friendships with jazz legends, his personal growth into manhood, and his exploration of various jazz styles. It delves into the emotional challenges he faced after undergoing brain surgery and his triumphant return to the stage, where he rekindled his connection with Blue Note. Martino also shares the serendipitous encounter with his wife and soulmate, Aya, in Japan, and discusses his philosophical perspective on "the here and now." The book adopts an immersive narrative approach through Martino's and Milkowski's internal perspectives, offering readers a vivid, first-hand account of Martino's historical journey.

This autobiography provides an in-depth exploration of the formative influence of guitarists such as Johnny Smith, Les Paul, and Wes Montgomery, revealing how Martino continuously refined and expanded his musical style. Furthermore, in an appendix, Martino outlines his unique perspective on guitar theory, detailing how he understands various triad types from the standpoint of augmented chords and conceptualizes other seventh chords on the basis of the diminished seventh chord. It also demonstrates his approach to visualizing different chord structures and interval relationships through geometric patterns, foundational knowledge that proves essential in the analysis of Martino's works.¹⁷

Another appendix features tributes from renowned guitarists such as John Scofield, Russell Malone, and Jonathan Kreisberg, who express their deep admiration and respect for Martino's contributions to the world of music.¹⁸

¹⁶ James Welsh Pepper, "Pat Martino: Here and Now," *YouTube video*, 2015, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Zip5SPAHy38>.

¹⁷ Martino and Milkowski, *Here and Now!*

¹⁸ Martino and Milkowski, *Here and Now!*, 101-118.

2.2.3 Pat Martino's The Nature of Guitar

In the interview portion of his course, *The Nature of Guitar*, Martino explores his unique understanding of guitar playing, musical improvisation, and creativity. He recalls his early experiences, particularly his fascination with his father's guitar, which was hidden under the bed and off-limits. This sense of rebellion and the allure of the forbidden became the foundation for his lifelong passion for the instrument.

Martino emphasizes the importance of imagination over rigid rules, highlighting that his initial interest in the guitar was driven by a desire for freedom rather than adherence to traditional learning methods. He often discusses his struggle with formal education and conventional approaches to learning music, viewing them as restrictive compared to his more intuitive, fluid way of exploring the guitar. This approach was reflected in his interactions with his mentor, Dennis Sandole, during his teenage years, when Martino found himself more inclined toward personal exploration rather than strictly following instructional guidance.

By contrasting improvisational spontaneity with structured learning, Martino underscores the significance of intuitive creativity over pre-planned execution. He describes music as an expression that transcends the physical limitations of the instrument, likening the guitar to a simple tool like a fork or knife used to enjoy a meal. For Martino, the true essence of music lies in the emotional and intuitive connection between the musician and the moment of creation rather than in technical perfection or rigid adherence to rules.

In this course, Martino conveys the idea that music is not just an art to be perfected but an ongoing journey filled with spontaneity, imagination, and emotional depth. He stresses that this perspective has shaped his distinctive personal style, ultimately allowing him to strike a balance between technical precision and an instinctive, creative connection to music.¹⁹

2.2.4 Tony Baruso's *Linear Expressions*

Tony Baruso's *Linear Expressions*, occupies a significant place in the academic study of jazz guitar. In this work, Baruso delves deeply into Pat Martino's

¹⁹ Pat Martino, *The Nature of Guitar*, <https://truefire.com/pat-martino/the-nature-of-guitar/c1002>.

distinctive approach to improvisation, based on his personal understanding of Martino's playing. The book's inception traces back to 1979, when Baruso studied under Martino at the Guitar Institute of Technology, a period of mentorship that afforded Baruso an insider's view of Martino's approach to improvisation.

Baruso provides a detailed exposition of Martino's theory of minor chord substitution, highlighting its differences from traditional improvisational techniques. He offers insights into how this approach diverges from conventional methods that rely on memorizing extensive scales and arpeggios. Instead, Martino's substitution concept focuses on simplifying complex chord progressions into minor chord forms. By internalizing five positional patterns of minor-chord bebop phrases across the entire fretboard and applying vertical and lateral modulations within each position, musicians can draw from a reservoir of accumulated minor chord lines. This approach allows for smoother and more coherent improvisational phrasing.

The book also includes a musical piece as a case study to demonstrate and analyze the chord substitution theory, providing readers with a glimpse of Martino's musical aesthetic in action. This analysis offers valuable perspectives for those seeking to explore and understand Martino's unique style of improvisation.²⁰

2.3 Literature Review of Analytical and Transcribing Method

2.3.1 Pat Martino's *Creative Force*

Pat Martino's *Creative Force* is a significant book on improvisation and harmonic theory. It explores the interval structures of different types of chords through concepts such as the "Diminished 7 Concept," the "Augmented Triad Concept," and the "Minor Conversion Concept." The book further demonstrates how complex chords can be transformed into minor modes during solos, using minor materials provided by Pat Martino as a foundation. By continually varying these materials, an improviser can create coherent and flowing melodic lines, enhancing the freedom and expressiveness of their music.

²⁰ Tony Baruso, *Linear Expressions* (HAL LEONARD CORPORATION, 1989).

Martino also emphasizes that to make playing second nature, one must internalize jazz vocabulary and truly understand improvisation rather than merely memorizing solos. This is particularly important for guitarists seeking to enhance their improvisational expression. Moreover, the improvisational concepts presented in these books are crucial for understanding and transcribing Pat Martino's own improvisations in his actual musical works.²¹

2.3.2 Pat Martino's Quantum Guitar: Complete

Pat Martino's *Quantum Guitar: Complete* is a comprehensive instructional resource divided into two sections: "Advanced Concepts" and "Analysis of a Tune."

The section called "Advanced Concepts" shows how to simplify harmonic structures, specifically by using minor triad materials to substitute for more complex harmonic progressions, thereby enhancing flexibility in improvisation. Martino emphasizes that by finding alternative choices for scales and chords, musicians can effectively reduce the cognitive load during improvisation. This method not only increases the freedom of improvisation but also makes the performance more coherent and expressive.

In "The Analysis of a Tune," Martino demonstrates how to apply these theories in real-world performance through the analysis of specific tunes. He meticulously dissects the melody, harmony, and rhythm, explaining how a deep understanding of the tune's structure can lead to personalized expression during improvisation. This allows players to internalize and truly hear the solo from within. This instructional resource is particularly valuable for musicians seeking to improve the precision of their transcriptions of Pat Martino's materials.²²

2.3.3 Hal Crook's How to Improvise: An Approach to Practicing Improvisation

In this book, Hal Crook begins by addressing key aspects such as rhythmic control, melodic development, phrase length, and complexity, offering a series of exercises designed to help students progress from basic to advanced improvisational

²¹ Kenn Aarson, Dave Debble, and Pat Martino, *Creative Force (1994)*.

²² *Quantum Guitar: Complete*, DVD, directed by Pat Martino (Warner Brothers Pub, 2008).

skills. The book emphasizes a “targeted practice” approach that involves gradually refining various aspects of improvisation through systematic practice to enhance performance abilities. Additionally, Crook explores how systematic limitations can be used to cultivate intuition and creativity in improvisation, ultimately making these instincts a natural part of musical performance – an idea that aligns closely with Pat Martino’s concept of developing a “second nature.” Crook provides comprehensive examples of performance techniques from multiple perspectives, including melody, rhythm, harmony, and ornamentation, most of which are applied to the analysis of Pat Martino’s improvisations in the six selected works.²³

2.3.4 Ted Pease’s Jazz Composition Theory And Practice

Ted Pease’s *Jazz Composition: Theory and Practice* is a classic work in the field of jazz composition education. It systematically explores theoretical concepts from scales and chords to melodic construction and harmonic applications, providing valuable reference materials for the analysis in Chapter IV. The book emphasizes the importance of understanding chord structures and their permutations to create flexible and complex harmonic effects, encouraging readers to master these foundational theories. These approaches offer valuable guidance for the transcription of Pat Martino’s works as well as a theoretical understanding of his performance style.²⁴

2.3.5 Ari Hoenig and Johannes Weidenmueller’s Intro to Polyrhythms: Contracting and Expanding Time Within Form

Ari Hoenig and Johannes Weidenmueller’s *Intro to Polyrhythms* is a seminal work on advanced rhythmic concepts in jazz and contemporary music. I explore the principles of polyrhythms from the perspective of various instruments, emphasizing techniques such as rhythm superimposition, metric modulation, and layered time signatures to manipulate rhythm and create intricate musical textures. Through a combination of practical exercises and theoretical explanations, the book provides tools

²³ Hal Crook, *How to Improvise: An Approach to Practicing Improvisation* (Rottenburg: Advance Music, 2005).

²⁴ Ted Pease, *Jazz Composition: Theory and Practice* (Rottenburg: Advance Music, 2003).

for the analysis and application of polyrhythms in composition and improvisation. This methodology is particularly useful for studying Pat Martino's rhythmic approaches, offering insights into how he uses rhythm as a tool for melodic and harmonic expression and providing essential theoretical support for understanding his works.²⁵

2.3.6 Bert Ligon's Jazz Theory Resources

Bert Ligon's *Jazz Theory Resources* is a systematic and comprehensive textbook on jazz improvisation and composition theory. Through structured pattern-based exercises, the book delves into core concepts such as scales, chords, arpeggios, and rhythmic frameworks, providing musicians with the tools to enhance their improvisational flexibility and harmonic understanding. The methodologies outlined in this text are particularly valuable for the analysis in Chapter IV of Pat Martino's playing style, offering significant insights into his approach to melodic construction and harmonic techniques.²⁶

2.3.7 Pat Martino's The Nature of Guitar

In *The Nature of Guitar*, Pat Martino provides an in-depth exploration of his understanding of augmented triads and diminished 7th chords through the use of triangles and rectangles. He shares how he uses the triad system to compose guitar solo pieces, explains his approach to using minor linear materials to interpret various types of dominant 7th and major 7th chords, and demonstrates, through practical examples, how he applies these concepts to real musical works. The course comprehensively showcases his personal approach to thinking about improvisation in real musical contexts. Mastering the content of this course can play a vital role in understanding Pat Martino's transcription and analysis.²⁷

2.3.8 Overview of Pat Martino's Stylistic Performance Methods

²⁵ Ari Hoenig and Johannes Weidenmueller, *Intro to Polyrhythms: Contracting and Expanding Time Within Form* (Pacific, MO: Mel Bay Publications, 2009), DVD included.

²⁶ Bert Ligon, *Jazz Theory Resources* (Houston Publishing, Inc., 2001).

²⁷ Martino, *The Nature of Guitar*.

I have dedicated significant time to studying and understanding all of Pat Martino’s instructional courses, books, and masterclasses, as well as spending extensive time transcribing and analyzing his historical recordings. This has given me insight into his unique playing habits and the thought processes that characterize his personal style. In this section, I will comprehensively analyze Pat Martino’s stylistic theories from an internal and personal perspective, drawing on Pat Martino’s *Creative Force*,²⁸ *Quantum Guitar: Complete*,²⁹ and *The Nature of Guitar*²⁷ as a technical and theoretical framework. These resources also include some of the analytical techniques used in Chapter IV.

Table 2.1 Pat Martino’s Triad Transformation (Inspired by theoretical concepts in *The Nature of Guitar*, which I have analyzed and adapted)

Triad	Transformation
CAug / EAug / AbAug	CAug=EAug=AbAug=C E Ab
Fm	E↑m2 (C Ab) → F C Ab=Fminor
Am	Ab↑m2 (C E) → A C E=Aminor
Dbm	C↑m2 (E Ab) → Db E Ab=Dbminor
Ab	E↓m2 (C Ab) → Eb C Ab=Abmajor
C	Ab↓m2 (C E) → G C E=Cmajor
E	C↓m2 (E Ab) → B E Ab=Emajor

Using the diminished 7th chord as a foundation, one can understand other types of seventh chords by raising or lowering chord tones by a half step. According to *The Nature of Guitar*, the diminished seventh chord serves as a structural basis for deriving various seventh chords through chromatic alterations. For example, Db dim7 = E dim7 = G dim7 = Bb dim7 = Db E G Bb. Lowering the E by a half step results in Eb Db G Bb = Eb7, which can in turn be transformed into Eb minor7 (Eb Gb Bb Db) by lowering the third (G) by a half step. Similarly, Eb7 can be transformed into Eb major7 (Eb G Bb D) by raising the seventh (Db) by a half step. Conversely, Db dim7 = E dim7 = G dim7 = Bb dim7 = Db E G Bb. Raising the E by a half step results in F Db G Bb = Gm7b5. By following the same logic, all 12 diminished seventh chords can be

²⁸ Aarson, Debbles, and Martino, *Creative Force*

²⁹ *Quantum Guitar: Complete*.

derived. Building upon this concept, understanding the constituent notes of seventh chords serves as the second step in Martino’s minor chord substitution theory system.

Table 2.2 Pat Martino’s 7th chord Transformation (Inspired by theoretical concepts in The Nature of Guitar, which I have analyzed and adapted)

7 th chord	Transformation
Dbdim7 / Edim7 / Gdim7 / Bbdim7	Dbdim7=Edim7=Gdim7=Bbdim7=Db E G Bb
Eb7	E↓m2 (Db G Bb)=Eb Db G Bb=Eb7
Gb7	G↓m2 (Db E Bb)=Gb Db E Bb=Gb7
A7	Bb↓m2 (Db E G)=A Db E G=A7
C7	Db↓m2 (E G Bb)=C E G Bb=C7
Gm7b5	E↑m2 (Db G Bb)=F Db G Bb=Gm7b5
Bbm7b5	G↑m2 (Db E Bb)=Ab Db E Bb=Bbm7b5
Dbm7b5	Bb↑m2 (Db E G)=B Db E G=Dbm7b5
Em7b5	Db↑m2 (E G Bb)=D E G Bb=Em7b5
Ebmajor7	Eb7→Db↑m2 (Eb G Bb)=Eb G Bb D=Ebmajor7
Gbmajor7	Gb7→E↑m2 (Gb Bb Db)=Gb Bb Db F=Gbmajor7
Amajor7	A7→G↑m2 (A C# E)=A C# E G#=Amajor7
Cmajor7	C7→Bb↑m2 (C E G)=C E G B=Cmajor7
Ebminor7	Eb7→G↓m2 (Eb Bb Db)=Eb Gb Bb Db=Ebminor7
Gbminor7	Gb7→Bb↓m2 (Gb Db E)=Gb A Db E =Gbminor7
Aminor7	A7→C#↓m2 (A E G)=A C E G=Aminor7
Cminor7	C7→E↓m2 (C G Bb)=C Eb G Bb=Cminor7

Table 2.3 Pat Martino’s basic chord substitution approach (Inspired by theoretical concepts in The Nature of Guitar, which I have analyzed and adapted)

Chords	Substitutions	Traditional Analysis
Gmajor7 (9 #11 13)	Eminor7 used over Gmajor7 (9 #11 13).	Eminor7 (E-G-B-D) corresponds to E Dorian (E-F#-G-A-B-C#-D-E) and, when applied over Gmajor7 (G-B-D-F#), creates a G Lydian sound (4th mode of the D major scale).
Gmajor7#5	Eminormajor7 used over Gmajor7#5.	Eminormajor7 (E-G-B-D#) corresponds to E melodic minor (E-F#-G-A-B-C-D#-E) and, when applied over Gmajor7#5 (G-B-D#-F#), creates

		a G Lydian Augmented sound (3rd mode of the E melodic minor scale).
Dbm7b5	Eminor7 used over Dbm7b5.	Eminor7 (E-G-B-D) corresponds to E Dorian (E-F#-G-A-B-C#-D-E) and, when applied over Dbm7b5 (Db-E-G-B), creates a Db Locrian sound (7rd mode of the D major scale).
	Eminormajor7 used over Dbm7b5.	Eminormajor7 (E-G-B-D#) corresponds to E melodic minor (E-F#-G-A-B-C-D#-E) and, when applied over Dbm7b5 (Db-E-G-B), creates a Db Locrian #2 sound (6th mode of the E melodic minor scale).
A7sus or A7 (9 #11 13). (Consonant dominant)	Eminor7 used over A7sus or A7 (9 13), but the unaltered tensions of A7 are described by Martino as “consonant dominant.”	Eminor7 (E-G-B-D) corresponds to E Dorian (E-F#-G-A-B-C#-D-E) and, when applied over A7sus or A7 (9 13), creates an A Mixlydian sound (5th mode of the D major scale).
	Eminormajor7 used over A7sus or A7 (9 #11 13), the unaltered tensions of A7 are summarized by Martino as “Consonant Dominant.”	Eminormajor7 (E-G-B-D#) corresponds to E melodic minor (E-F#-G-A-B-C-D#-E) and, when applied over A7sus or A7 (9 #11 13), creates an A Lydianb7 sound (4th mode of the E melodic minor scale).
A7#11, A7b13, A7#9, A7b9, A7b9b13. (Dissonant dominant)	Bbminormajor7 DbmMajor7 EmMajor7 GmMajor7 used over A7#11, A7b13, A7#9, A7b9, A7b9b13. (Multiple Substitutions)	Bbminormajor7 (Bb-Db-F-A) corresponds to Bb melodic minor (Bb-C-Db-Eb-F-G-A-Bb) and, when applied over A7 (A-C#-E-G), creates an A altered (Aalt) sound (7th mode of the Bb melodic minor scale).
		Eminormajor7 (E-G-B-D#) corresponds to E melodic minor (E-F#-G-A-B-C#-D#-E) and, when applied over A7 (A-C#-E-G), produces an A7 (9 #1113) sound (4th mode of the E melodic minor scale).

		<p>Gminormajor7 (G-Bb-D-Gb) corresponds to G melodic minor (G-A-Bb-C-D-E-Gb-G) and, when applied over A7 (A-C#-E-G), generates an A7sus (b9 b13) sound (2th mode of the G melodic minor scale).</p>
		<p>Dbminormajor7 (Db-E-Ab-C) corresponds to Db melodic minor (Db-Eb-E-Gb-Ab-Bb-C-Db), and its application over A7 (A-C#-E-G) creates an A7 (b9 #9 #11) sound. Unlike the other substitutions, this does not correspond to any specific traditional modal framework of the melodic minor scale. Instead, it expands the harmonic palette, emphasizing tonal ambiguity and heightened tension through unconventional intervallic relationships.</p>

Extending an in-depth understanding of Pat Martino’s minor chord substitution framework, this study will further summarize his frequently mentioned concept of “linear expressions” and examine its foundations.

In Pat Martino’s theory, “linear” refers to the horizontal movement of music across the guitar fretboard, emphasizing the melodic and scalar continuity of linear motion. It contrasts with the “vertical” structure of chords and focuses on constructing fluidity and coherence in music through the linear arrangement of notes, the use of scale patterns, and the development of melodic lines. Because Martino preferred to substitute all chords with minor chords, his “linear expression” is more effectively achieved through minor-mode materials.³⁰

³⁰ Martino, *The Nature of Guitar*.

However, Martino acknowledges that different musicians adopt varying modes of thought. Some prefer using major linear materials or even any variation thereof, describing this approach as “magic.” As Martino himself has stated: “If you are good at one thing, you are good at all things. You must see them for what they are, and not fall prey to the many masks they’d wear.”³¹

Substitution Application:

Based on the understanding of the previous content of Pat Martino’s Basic Chord Substitution approach, we can derive the following more direct application rules:

CMajor7: Express using A minor linear materials.

CMinor7: Express using C minor linear materials.

C7 (not resolving to a stable chord): Express using G minor linear materials.

C7 Alt(resolving to a stable chord, multiple substitution): Express using E minor, Db minor, Bb minor, or G minor linear materials.

CMinor7b5: Express using Eb minor linear materials.

Drawing on his deep understanding of triads, 7th chords, Martino analyzed various types of complex chords and discovered that these chords can all be expressed using minor triads, minor 7th, or minor-major 7th forms. In the case of dissonant dominants, he created his own “multiple substitutions” system based on his playing experience. Martino’s system may differ from traditional music theory but provides a more diverse approach to the expression of harmonic color.³⁰

For the minor linear materials, Martino employed his decades of performance experience to deliver an expressive interpretation of the composition. He expressed in a public lecture that he used linear materials taken from bebop and based on minor scales. In other words, he did not practice minor scales in a strictly scalar manner, but rather through imitation and transcription of the giants he admired in his early years. His playing exhibits a diverse range of variations on minor scales, shaped by his perception, experience, emotions, and harmonic context. These variations in the minor scales are heavily influenced by his deep understanding of the bebop musical language and his decades of playing experience.³²

³¹ Pat Martino, *In The Style of Pat Martino*, <https://www.dc-musicschool.com>

³² Dave Frank, “Dave Frank Jazz Master Class - An Evening with Pat Martino.”

Building upon a comprehensive understanding of Martino’s entire theoretical framework, I have investigated the guitar performance techniques that he employs in his live musical renditions. In the following section, I reveal the foundational theory behind Pat Martino’s guitar special techniques through the transcription and analysis of selected excerpts from his musical works.

Double-Stops

Martino often employs double-stops and repetitive phrases with a blues characteristic in his music. These make up an indispensable part of his playing style. The following example (2.1) clearly illustrates his use of blues-style double-stops within the Fm Blues materials add $\flat 3$ in a jazz blues tune, as well as repetitive embellishments using semitone slide techniques, eliciting an emotional response from the audience.

Example 2.1 “Bar Wars,” mm. 177-178

Example 2.2 showcases how Martino uses the double-stop technique to create repetitive riffs, which is a great tool for driving emotion.

Example 2.2 “Bar Wars,” mm. 181-182

Slide Combined with The-3 Against-4 Technique

Every guitarist around the world is familiar with the following example. Martino uses C as a pivot note, then slides from D \sharp to E, extensively repeating these three notes, combining bluesy slide techniques with a polyrhythmic application of 3-against-4.

Example 2.3 “Sunny” (2002), mm. 81-82

Open String and String Pull-off Combined with 3-Against-4 Technique

In the next example (2.4), Martino skillfully employs the open E string as a pivot note, then combines string pull-off techniques to integrate the originally grouped three notes into a 4/4 context, using a polyrhythmic application of 3-against-4 to create an aural displacement. This technique is a hallmark of Martino’s distinctive personal style.

Example 2.4 “Sunny” (2014), mm. 85-86

Economic Picking

Pat Martino’s exceptional right-hand picking technique, particularly his use of economic picking, vividly demonstrates his mastery of string picking, a skill admired and praised by contemporaries such as George Benson.³³ In the solo, Martino showcases his picking abilities, utilizing economy picking to great effect. This technique also ranks as one of the most defining characteristics of Martino’s playing style.

Example 2.5 “Just Friends,” mm. 57

Alternate Picking

Martino’s improvisational solos feature extensive alternate picking, which tests the guitarist’s right-hand picking ability. The fast and densely-packed notes in

³³ Pat Martino, *Open Road*.

“Impressions” present a significant challenge for guitarists. To play with the speed, complexity, and energy displayed by Martino, while infusing the bluesy feel, requires a deep appreciation for his solo and diligent emulation.

Example 2.6 “Impressions,” mm. 61-63

String Bend

The playing style illustrated in example 2.7 exemplifies a technique that became particularly prominent in Martino’s later live improvisations. This technique serves as a powerful means of expressing one’s emotions, akin to the exclamation of “yeah, yeah, yeah!”

Example 2.7 “Catch” (1995), mm. 129-131

Stairway Chromaticism

In long melodic lines, Martino frequently transitions from the higher positions on the guitar. Example 2.8 demonstrates the use of the index and ring fingers to execute rapid alternations across different strings, achieving chromatic shifts that gradually descend to the lower positions. The resolution from tension to release is masterfully executed, a feature of Martino’s playing style throughout his career. Pat Martino likened the different positions on the guitar to various floors of a house, with the chromatic connections serving as the stairs between these levels, moving from dissonance to consonance.

Example 2.8 “Sunny” (DC Music version), mm. 81

<i>Baiyina</i>	1968	Bobby Rose–guitar Gregory Herbert–alto sax flute Richard Davis–bass Charlie Persip–drums Reggie Ferguson–tabla Balakrishna–tamboura	Prestige
<i>Desperado</i>	1970	Eddie Green–electric piano Tyrone Brown–electric bass Sherman Ferguson–drums Eric Kloss–alto sax, soprano sax	Prestige
<i>The Visit!</i>	1972	Bobby Rose–guitar Richard Davis–bass Billy Higgins–drums	Cobblestone (Reissued on Muse Records as Footprints)
<i>Live!</i>	1972	Ron Thomas–electric piano Tyrone Brown–electric bass Sherman Ferguson–drums	Muse
<i>Consciousness</i>	1974	Eddie Green–electric piano Tyrone Brown–electric bass Sherman Ferguson–drums	Muse
<i>Exit</i>	1976	Gil Goldstein–piano Richard Davis–bass Billy Hart–drum	Muse
<i>We'll Be Together Again</i>	1976	Gil Goldstein–electric piano	Muse
<i>Starbright</i>	1976	Gil Goldstein–keyboards Warren Bernhardt–synthesizer Will Lee–electric bass Mike Mainieri–synthesizer Michael Carvin–drums Charles Collins–drums Alyrio Lima–percussion Marty Quinn–tabla Albert Regni–flute Joe d' Onofrio–violin (Pat introduces guitar synthesizer here)	Warner Bros

<i>Joyous Lake</i>	1977	Delmar Brown, Fender Rhodes– synthesizer Mark Leonard–electric bass Kenwood Dennard–drums	Warner Bros
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Table 2.4 Pat Martino’s Discography (cont.)

Album	Recorded Years	Personnel	Recorded by
<i>The Return</i>	1989	Steve LaSpina–drums Joey Baron–drums	Muse
<i>Interchange</i>	1994	James Ridl–piano Marc Johnson–bass Sherman Ferguson–drums	Muse
<i>The Maker</i>	1995	James Ridl–piano Marc Johnson–bass Joe Bonadio–drums	Evidence
<i>Night Wings</i>	1996	James Ridl–piano Bob Kenmotsu–tenor sax Marc Johnson–bass Bill Stewart– drums	Muse
<i>All Sides Now</i>	1997	Mike Stern–guitar Tuck Andress–guitar Charlie Hunter–guitar Kevin Eubanks–guitar Michael Hedges–guitar Joe Satriani–guitar Les Paul–guitar Lou Pollo–guitar Cassandra Wilson–vocals Scott Amendola–drums Ben Perowsky–drums Jeff Hirshfield–drums Scott Colley–bass Paul Nowinski–bass	Blue Note

<i>Stone Blue</i>	1998	Delmar Brown–keyboards James Genus–bass Eric Alexander–tenor sax Kenwood Dennard–drums	Blue Note
<i>Fire Dance</i>	1999	Peter Block–flute Habib Khan–sitar Zakir Hussain–tablas Ilya Razman–violin	Mythos
<i>Live at Yoshi's</i>	2001	Joey DeFrancesco–organ Billy Hart–drums	Blue Note
<i>Think Tank</i>	2003	Joe Lovano–tenor sax Gonzalo Rubalcaba–piano Christian McBride–bass Lewis Nash–drums	Blue Note
<i>Remember: A Tribute to Wes Montgomery</i>	2006	David Kikoski–piano John Patitucci–bass Scott Allan Robinson–drums Daniel Sadownick–percussion	Blue Note
<i>Live at Blues Alley</i>	2011	Tony Monaco, organ Eric Alexander–tenor sax Jeff “Tain” Watts–drums	HighNote
<i>Formidable</i>	2017	Pat Martino–guitar Pat Bianchi–organ Carmen Intorre Jr.–drums Adam Niewood–tenor saxophone (tracks 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, and 9) Alex Norris– trumpet (tracks 1, 3, 5, 7, and 9), flugelhorn (track 2)	HighNote

CHAPTER III

METHODOLOGY

The primary methodologies employed in this research include a comprehensive literature review and an in-depth analysis of guitar solo transcriptions, with no focus on guitar comping analysis. This study refers to Pat Martino's "second nature" learning method, as discussed in J.W. Pepper's *Pat Martino: Here and Now*, in its use of high levels of focus and extensive repetition as the core approach to transcription. This method was used to obtain complete transcriptions of six selected works from different periods of Martino's career. Subsequently, theoretical analysis techniques drawn from relevant literature were applied to these transcriptions to gain a more comprehensive understanding of Martino's playing characteristics and thought processes. Following the completion of the theoretical analysis, I drew on my personal experience to design structured exercises that help musicians effectively internalize and apply Martino's theories and techniques within practical performance settings.

3.1 Selection of Compositions for Musical Analysis

3.1.1 "Just Friends"

This piece featured on Pat Martino's second album, *El Hombre* (1967), with band members including Danny Turner on flute, Trudy Pitts on Hammond organ, Mitch Fine on drums, Vance Anderson on bongos, and Abdu Johnson on congas. In his autobiography, Martino mentions that due to Vanguard Records signing Larry Coryell, he had to delay by a year the release of his first album, which he had already recorded. It was produced by Chuck Israels and featured such notable musicians as Ron Carter, Tommy Flanagan, and Tony Williams, but was never released. The following year, his

second album, *El Hombre*, was released, which Martino described as “essentially an extension of my interest in Wes Montgomery.”³⁵

3.1.2 “Joyous Lake”

“Joyous Lake,” composed by Pat Martino, was featured on the 1977 album of the same name. The album was recorded in September 1976, and brought together an impressive ensemble, including Delmar Brown on electric piano, Kenwood Dennard on bass, and Allen Schwartzberg on drums. Reflecting on the title, Kenwood Dennard remarked that the true essence of “Joyous Lake” translates to “perseverance perseveres.” This sentiment seems especially fitting for Pat Martino, a musician who embodied resilience more than most, making the title a perfect representation of his life and spirit. To record *Joyous Lake*, the band traveled to Criteria Studios in Miami. During the sessions, they witnessed an unidentified flying object over the beach, adding an air of mystery to the recording experience and infusing the album with an otherworldly ambiance.³⁵

3.1.3 “Turnpike”

“Turnpike,” composed by Pat Martino, was featured on his 1989 album *The Return*, recorded in February 1987 with Steve LaSpina on bass and Joey Baron on drums. Following his surgery in 1980, Martino relearned guitar with the support of friends and students, ultimately marking his official comeback with *The Return* in 1987. “Turnpike,” one of the standout tracks on the album, showcases Martino’s remarkable technical skill and offers a fresh perspective on hard bop through his unique interpretative lens.³⁵

3.1.4 “Think Tank”

“Think Tank,” composed by Pat Martino, was featured on his 2003 album of the same name, recorded from January 8 to 10, 2003, with a distinguished ensemble including Joe Lovano on tenor saxophone, Gonzalo Rubalcaba on piano, Christian McBride on bass, and Lewis Nash on drums. In the early stages of composing this piece, Martino recalled a student who was strongly interested in John Coltrane’s “Giant Steps.”

³⁵ Pat Martino and Bill Milkowski, *Here and Now!*

The song's rapid chord changes make it challenging to perform. However, for Martino, complexity and simplicity are merely two sides of the same coin. He developed a unique system by mapping the 26 letters of the alphabet to a minor scale, then used notes from Coltrane's corresponding tenor sax scale to construct the thematic foundation of "Think Tank."³⁶

3.1.5 "Lean Year"

"Lean Years," composed by Pat Martino in 1967, was featured on the album *Strings!* recorded on October 2, 1967. The recording featured Cedar Walton on piano, Joe Farrell on tenor saxophone and flute, Ben Tucker on bass, and Walter Perkins on drums. The song reflects Pat Martino's challenging experiences while living in New York City. During this time, Martino faced financial difficulties, often driving a taxi to make ends meet. The title of the piece captures the essence of those tough times. Martino mentioned that the core melody of this track came to him in just a few seconds, but it took years before he would learn how to properly write and notate music. He learned primarily through his experiences on the streets and by playing with some of the great musicians of that era. By observing and seeking help from others, he gradually mastered the skills needed to create and document his music.³⁷

3.1.6 "Full House"

The original version of "Full House" was composed by Wes Montgomery, recorded on June 25, 1962, and featured on the album *Full House*. It features a hard bop style filled with dynamic rhythm and improvisation. As a teenager, Pat Martino was heavily influenced by Wes Montgomery, often transcribing his solos. Martino mentioned that in the early hours of one morning in 1963, he had breakfast with Wes Montgomery, Grant Green, Les Paul, and George Benson, discussing guitar until sunrise, forming a deep friendship. Martino reinterpreted "Full House" in his 2006 album

³⁶ Pat Martino and Bill Milkowski, *Here and Now!*

³⁷ JazzBridge, "Pat Martino - Lean Years," YouTube, 2016, video, 3:20, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UCF0vcvvrzc>.

Remember: A Tribute to Wes Montgomery, paying homage to his idol and their close bond.³⁶

Table 3.1 Overview of selected repertoire

Song Title - Composer	Style	Tempo (bpm) / Key	Number of measures transcribed
“Just Friends” - John Klenner	Hard bop 4/4 Up tempo - Swing	240/Fmajor	98
“Joyous Lake” - Pat Martino	Fusion 6/4 Polyrhythmic Bossa	250/Dmajor	72
“Turnpike” - Pat Martino	Hard bop 4/4 Up tempo - Swing	250/No Fixed key center	65
“Think Tank” - Pat Martino	Post bop 4/4 Up Medium Swing	165/No Fixed key center	89
“Lean Year” - Pat Martino	Hard bop 4/4 Up tempo - Swing	240/No Fixed key center	128
“Full House” - Wes Montgomery	Hard bop 3/4 Up tempo - Swing	200/Fm	136

3.2 Transcribing Method and Process

The transcription method employed in this study is rooted in the concept of “second nature,” a state achieved through intense focus and repeated practice, wherein musical technique and artistry become an instinctive extension of the musician. This method represents an advanced level of musicianship in which instrumental technique and internal aural artistry are seamlessly integrated, which facilitates the complete

internalization of the music. This chapter provides a detailed and systematic exploration of the transcription process.

Martino highlighted that students often excessively transcribe without understanding the emotional and contextual elements behind the music. In reality, music is not only created by the performer but is also shaped by the surrounding environment. Transcription is a useful tool, but it is crucial to try to understand and feel the context and emotional components of the piece at the time of its creation. Therefore, prior to commencing the transcription process, I conducted a thorough study of the historical context in an attempt to discern Martino's emotional intent at the time of performance. This was followed by imitating and performing the articulation of the melodies in these pieces. Subsequently, I committed the original melody and harmony to memory before proceeding to transcribe the guitar solo section. It is important to note that my transcription is exclusively focused on the guitar solo and does not include the comping.

In addition, Martino's learning method places a strong emphasis on focus and repetition, making repeated listening to the recordings being transcribed one of the most crucial steps in the process. Since early 2022, I have listened daily to Pat Martino's works, which has given me a deep familiarity with the six pieces analyzed in this study, particularly their melodic sections. This extensive listening experience has had a significant impact on the accuracy and depth of the transcription work.

To internalize musical vocabulary, it is essential to repeatedly sing along with the solos while listening to them until they can be performed unconsciously. This process demands significant mental perseverance, embodying the "indomitable" spirit that Pat Martino conveyed to the world. I used software called Bandlab to slow down the playback speed to help me internalize the melodies. This process involved repeatedly singing along with specific sections of the recording until I could unconsciously follow along at a moderate tempo. Subsequently, I moved to replicating the solos on the guitar.

The guitar requires players to use their ability to visualize intervals on the fretboard to remember solos. This visualization method helps translate melodies in the mind into instrument performance, so developing the ability to think visually is very important. Repeatedly practicing solos will naturally enhance this ability. Throughout the entire transcription process, I adhered strictly to these methods until I had fully memorized all solo sections. Bandlab played an important role in the learning process,

enabling me to absorb more detailed aspects of the performance, thereby continuously improving my playing skills and musical expressiveness. When I could play along with the recordings on the guitar, I began notating the scores in Sibelius, using my instrument as a reference tool to ensure the accurate transcription of each note of the solos, thereby laying the foundation for subsequent analysis.

Table 3.2 Research process – time allocation for individual phases

Song Title	Intensive listening (days)	Melody Learning (days)	Sing the solo with recording (days)	Guitar Play-Along (days)	Write down the solo (days)	Analysis (days)	Total (days)
“Just Friend”	7	1	3	4	3	3	21
“Joyous Lake”	7	1	3	4	3	3	21
“Turnpike”	7	2	3	4	4	3	23
“Think Tank”	7	1	3	5	4	3	23
“Lean Year”	7	2	3	5	4	3	24
“Full House”	7	2	3	4	4	3	23

3.3 Analytical Technique

Having visualized the solos on the guitar using Pat Martino’s theoretical framework and meticulously notated the required solo sections for each piece in Sibelius, the next step involved analyzing the key solo segments. The primary analytical tools and techniques used in this study are derived from the following materials: Pat Martino’s *Creative Force*,³⁸ Pat Martino’s *Quantum Guitar: Complete*,³⁹ Hal Crook’s *How to*

³⁸ Aarson, Debble, and Martino, *Creative Force*.

³⁹ *Quantum Guitar: Complete*.

Improvise: An Approach to Practicing Improvisation,⁴⁰ Ted Pease's Jazz Composition Theory And Practice,⁴¹ Ari Hoenig and Johannes Weidenmueller's Intro to Polyrhythms: Contracting and Expanding Time Within Form,⁴² Bert Ligon's Jazz Theory Resources,⁴³ Pat Martino's The Nature of Guitar,⁴⁴ and Pat Martino's Stylistic Performance Methods.

The following are the improvisational analysis techniques involved in the study of Pat Martino's solos:

Melodic Construction Analysis:

Sequence: Transposing a melodic fragment or phrase to a different pitch level. This transposition can be diatonic, preserving the original tonality, or exact, potentially implying a temporary key-of-the-moment. The use of sequences expands upon the concept of repetition, introducing both melodic and rhythmic variety, thereby enhancing the overall complexity and interest of the musical passage.

Example 3.1 Motivic sequence

Example 3.2 Melodic sequence

Intervallic transformation: same rhythm, different pitches.

Example 3.3 Intervallic transformation

⁴⁰ Crook, *How to Improvise*.

⁴¹ Pease, *Jazz Composition*.

⁴² Hoenig and Weidenmueller, *Intro to Polyrhythms*, DVD included.

⁴³ Ligon, *Jazz Theory Resources*.

⁴⁴ Martino, *The Nature of Guitar*.

Rhythmic transformation: same pitches, different rhythm.

Example 3.4 Rhythmic transformation

Pedal tone: A figure where the pivot notes stay fixed as the melodic line progresses. In example 3.5, the original melodic line, G-F-E-D, is embellished with pivot notes to enhance its musical interest.

Example 3.5 Pedal tone

Octave Displacement: Shifting notes by an octave to create variation and extend the melodic line, adding interest and complexity to the phrasing.

Example 3.6 Octave Displacement

Passing tones (PT): Notes that move stepwise between two pitches, typically connecting non-adjacent chord tones.

Example 3.7 Passing tones

Neighbor tones (NT): Notes that move stepwise away from a primary note and then return to it or proceed directly to a target note without preparation.

Example 3.8 Neighbor tones

Indirect resolution (IR): Two notes of brief and equal duration that approach the target note stepwise from both above and below

Example 3.9 Indirect resolution

Chromatic approach (CH): Connection between two notes separated by a major second through a half-step.

Example 3.10 Chromatic approach

Double chromatic approach (DCHR): Two notes of short and equal duration that move by consecutive half steps to a target note.

Example 3.11 Double chromatic approach

Enclosure: A melodic device in which a target note is approached by its notes below and above.

Example 3.12 Enclosure

Rhythmic Analysis:

Rhythmic anticipation (A): When a note that would typically fall on the beat is played either a half beat or a full beat earlier. When a chord change is present, the chord itself is also anticipated, contributing to a sense of forward motion in the music.

Example 3.13 Rhythmic anticipation

A delayed attack (DA): When a note that would typically be played on the beat is instead played half a beat or a full beat later. In cases involving a chord change, the progression of the chord is also delayed accordingly.

Example 3.14 A delayed attack

Rhythmic Displacement: When a motif's rhythm is repeated but shifted to start on a different beat within the measure. For instance, if the original motif begins on the first beat in 4/4 time, the displaced version might start on the second, third, or fourth beat while maintaining the original rhythmic pattern.

Example 3.15 Rhythmic Displacement

Double Time: Double time is a musical effect that occurs when one or more performers make the tempo appear to be twice as fast as the original tempo

Example 3.16 Double Time

Superimposed Metric modulation: Layering one rhythm or pulse over another to create the illusion of a temporary tempo change while maintaining the original tempo.

Example 3.17 Superimposed Metric Modulation

Syncopation: Accenting certain beats within a measure—whether downbeats or upbeats—that are typically unaccented, enhancing the rhythmic feel of the music and creating a sense of forward momentum.

Example 3.18 Syncopation

Rhythmic Density: Playing many notes, typically using shorter rhythmic values such as eighth notes, triplets, and sixteenth notes, though longer note values may occasionally be included. Such phrases, referred to as “dense” or “active” phrases, can vary in length and often convey a sense of busyness or complexity.

Example 3.19 Rhythmic Density

Bopping the Top: A jazz technique where accents are placed on the top notes of a melodic line or at direction changes, creating a counter-rhythm to the underlying

pulse, often resulting in dotted quarter note rhythms and contributing to polyrhythmic complexity.

Example 3.20 Bopping the Top

Harmonic Analysis:

Minor Substitution: substituting a related minor chord for whatever chord is being played at the time; In Example 3.8, A minor materials are used over different types of chords.

Example 3.21 Minor Substitution

Upper structure: Any triad that consists of chord tones and allowable tensions derived from the chord scale. Importantly, it must contain at least one allowable tension.

Example 3.22 Upper structure

Polychords: The superimposition of one chord over a foundational chord, which can be a seventh chord. When the superimposed chord is a seventh chord, this typically results in more complex and rich harmonic textures.

Example 3.23 Polychords

Digital pattern: When patterns are structured according to the numerical value of each note in relation to the underlying chord or scale.

Example 3.24 Digital pattern

Special Techniques Analysis:

Double-Stops: playing two notes simultaneously, often used to create harmonic richness or emphasize a bluesy sound.

Example 3.25 Double-Stops

Slide Combined with The 3-Against-4 Technique:

Example 3.26 Slide Combined with The 3-Against-4 Technique

Open String and String Pull-off Combined with 3-Against-4 Technique:

Example 3.27 Open String and String Pull-off Combined with 3-Against-4 Technique

Economic Picking: Incorporating directional picking into alternate picking technique.

Example 3.28 Economic Picking

String Bend: When the string is pushed or pulled to change the pitch, adding expressiveness and emotional depth to the note.

Example 3.29 String Bend

Stairway Chromaticism: Alternating notes between two adjacent strings to form chromatic sequences, highlighting the characteristics of different guitar strings.

Example 3.30 Stairway Chromaticism

Octave Chromatic Displacement: Shifting notes by an octave to create chromatic scale variation and extend the melodic line, adding interest and complexity to the phrasing.

Example 3.31 Octave Chromatic Displacement

3.4 Guiding Practice Methods

After completing the transcription and analysis, I designed a systematic approach to assimilating Pat Martino's unique playing style. This approach is organized into five progressive topics: (1) all chords converted to minor, (2) embellishments' practices, (3) long phrases in Pat Martino's style, (4) special guitar techniques, and (5) comprehensive application. These topics build upon one another in a logical sequence, enabling musicians to absorb and apply Martino's distinctive techniques progressively. The specific content of each topic will be thoroughly discussed in Chapter Five.

CHAPTER IV ANALYSIS

4.1 “Just Friends” Analysis

4.1.1 Background Information

“Just Friends” is a classic jazz standard composed by John Klenner, with lyrics by Sam M. Lewis. Pat Martino’s interpretation is typically rendered in the key of F major. The piece is characterized by its 240bpm up-tempo 4/4 swing feel and adheres to a traditional 32-measure ABAC form. Martino reinterpreted “Just Friends” in his distinctive style, drawing on influences from Wes Montgomery, Les Paul, and Johnny Smith. His rendition left a profound impact on countless jazz musicians and further cemented his legacy in jazz history.

In this study, the analysis of “Just Friends” lays the groundwork for an exploration of Martino’s personal playing style. The following sections will provide a comprehensive analysis of a 98-measure transcription, highlighting the most representative segments for detailed discussion and presentation.

Table 4.1 Structure of “Just Friends”

Measure	[1-8]	[9-40]	[41-136]	[137-232]	[233-264]	[265-340]
Time Span	0: 00- 0: 08	0: 09- 0: 40	0: 41- 2: 17	2: 18- 3: 55	3: 56- 4: 28	4: 29- 5: 49
	Intro Organ solo	Head in (used for analysis)	Guitar solo (used for analysis)	Organ solo	Head out	Outro Guitar solo
Number of measures	8 measures	32 measures	96 measures	96 measures	32 measures	76 measures

4.1.2 Melodic Construction Analysis

Pat Martino often skillfully employs motivic transformation in his improvisations to enrich and expand his expressive range. In measures 39-40 (Example 4.1), Martino develops motif using intervallic transformation techniques. The first phrase implies the sound of F major seventh sharp fifth, but Martino tends to classify it within D minor materials, while the second phrase uses E \flat minor materials, creating the sound of F7 \flat 9. He uses rhythmic sequencing in the melody to develop the motif, while progressively lowering the pitch, resulting in a seamless connection to the beginning of the first chorus solo. This transition allows the music to resolve appropriately in terms of both auditory continuity and emotional impact.

Example 4.1 “Just Friends,” mm. 39-40

The second phrase occurs in measures 42-43 (Example 4.2). Martino employs a chromatic scale to connect B \flat major seventh and B \flat minor seventh. Additionally, in measure 44, he uses pivot tones (B \flat) to create the minor third and major second intervals.

Example 4.2 “Just Friends,” mm. 42-44

In measures 87-88 (Example 4.3), Martino uses intervallic transformation to develop the motif. The first phrase consists of an arpeggio based on G minor ninth, while the second phrase features an arpeggio of G flat minor major seventh (G \flat A D \flat F), with the added 9th (A \flat), considering the context of F7 alt . Furthermore, Martino omits the C7 chord in this context. When the F7 functions as an altered dominant,

Martino employs a minor substitution a minor second above, which adds tension and excitement to the solo. This approach enhances the sense of resolution from measure 88 to measure 89.

87 Gm^7 C^7 F^7

Intervallic transformation

Example 4.3 “Just Friends,” mm. 87-88

Martino is skilled at using chromatic approach techniques to embellish notes, a style that musicians have widely emulated. In measure 46 (Example 4.4), he first approaches the seventh of the chord, followed by the fifth. In measure 47, he initially uses the chromatic approach to target the $b9$, creating tension and then approaches the root to create a sense of resolution. In measure 48, he approaches the 9 of the chord first, followed by the $b7$, effectively adding depth to his phrasing.

Below Approach

46 F^{maj7} Abm^7 Db^7

Example 4.4 “Just Friends,” mm. 46-48

In measure 61 (Example 4.5), Martino outlines the chord tones of F major seventh while adding the 9th and 13th, enriching the harmonic color of the entire measure. In measure 62, he uses chromatic techniques to connect to the fifth of the chord, then employs octave displacement as an embellishment technique to expand the interval creatively. He then incorporates the $\#11$, adding a Lydian color that enhances the melodic interest. In measure 63, Martino uses the 9th, 11th, and a chromatic note above the root to create a sense of tension.

Example 4.5 “Just Friends,” mm. 61-63

In measures 111-112 (Example 4.6), Martino embellishes the melody with enclosure techniques centered around the Bb note and B.

Example 4.6 “Just Friends,” mm. 111-112

4.1.3 Rhythmic Analysis

Rhythmic anticipation is a key element of Pat Martino’s improvisational style, and three rhythmic anticipations can be found in “Just Friends.” In measures 75-76 (Example 4.7), 104-105 (Example 4.8), and 133-134 (Example 4.9), Martino moves the harmony forward by half a beat.

Example 4.7 “Just Friends,” mm. 75-76

Example 4.8 “Just Friends,” mm. 104-105

Example 4.9 “Just Friends,” mm. 133-134

In measure 91 (Example 4.10), Martino uses three notes, Ab-Db-Ab, derived from the chord tones of Bb minor seventh, employing bopping the top to create rhythmic ambiguity. As discussed in Chapter 2, Martino often incorporates open strings or slides while simultaneously applying the three-note accent displacement technique. This distinctive playing style has become widely recognized and admired by jazz musicians worldwide.

Example 4.10 “Just Friends,” mm. 91

In measures 129-132(Example 4.11), Martino maintains his characteristic use of high rhythmic density, a hallmark of his playing style throughout his career. In fact, the rhythmic intensity is consistently dense throughout the entire solo, presenting significant challenges for most guitarists. This level of complexity demands exceptional precision in both pick technique and coordination between the left and right hands, pushing technical abilities to their limits.

Example 4.11 “Just Friends,” mm. 129-132

In measures 109-110(Example 4.12), Martino employs syncopation by incorporating rests to emphasize offbeats at unexpected positions. This technique serves as a moment of contrast and reprieve following the high rhythmic density passages, functioning as both an expressive tool to convey his personal emotions and a preparatory device for the next surge of high rhythmic density playing.

The image shows a musical staff in treble clef with a key signature of one flat (Bb). The music starts at measure 109, indicated by a small '109' above the staff. A bracket above the staff spans the first two measures and is labeled 'Syncopation'. The first measure contains a chord labeled 'Fmaj7' above it. The melody consists of eighth notes and quarter notes with syncopated rhythms, including rests in the middle of measures.

Example 4.12 “Just Friends,” mm. 109-110

4.1.4 Harmonic Analysis

In measure 53-54 (Example 4.13), Pat Martino employs a D minormajor seventh(ninth) arpeggio, consisting of D-F-A-C#-E over a G7, followed by a chromatic approach from the note Eb to D. To interpret this example using the theoretical framework outlined in Chapter 2, the first step involves visualizing the Ab diminished seventh. By lowering the chord tone Ab by a half-step, one arrives at the G7, yielding the chord tones G-B-D-F. Extending this to G9 (G-B-D-F-A) reveals that G9 is equivalent to D minor sixth over G (D minor sixth / G). This connection aligns D minor sixth with the D minor, linking it further to the D minor materials category discussed in Chapter 2. This cyclical thought process exemplifies a closed-loop methodology that is central to Martino’s harmonic approach. It also highlights that Martino often interprets G7, G9, G7sus, and G13 chords through the lens of minor substitution materials derived from the perfect fifth above the dominant chord’s root. This conceptual framework is crucial for understanding his improvisational style and its distinctive harmonic logic.

The image shows a musical staff in treble clef with a key signature of one flat (Bb). The music starts at measure 53, indicated by a small '53' above the staff. A bracket above the staff spans the first two measures and is labeled 'D minor materials'. The first measure contains a chord labeled 'G7' above it. The melody consists of eighth notes and quarter notes, including a chromatic approach from Eb to D in the second measure.

Example 4.13 “Just Friends,” mm. 53-54

In measure 57 (Example 4.14), Martino defines the line’s contour through different octaves of F, which functions as the fifth degree in the Bb major scale and a chord tone in Bb major seventh, while using eighth-note rests to embellish the melodic line. In measure 58, he employs a G minor substitution to extend over the Bb major

seventh chord, utilizing the melodic embellishment technique of enclosure with the melody C-A-Bb-C, creating a distinct melodic color and auditory effect. This also demonstrates Martino’s skill in applying relative minor materials over major chords, a distinctive aspect of his improvisational style.

Example 4.14 “Just Friends,” mm. 57-58

In measures 49-52 (Example 4.15), Pat Martino demonstrates his unique approach to handling consonant dominant chords and dissonant dominant chords with minor substitution and his use of major-seventh arpeggios over minor-seventh chords. These characteristics are crucial for anyone aiming to emulate his distinctive sound. In measure 49, he uses eighth-note rests and diatonic notes to embellish chord tones, connecting them to the next measure. In measure 50, he employs a minor substitution derived from the perfect fifth above the root of the C7 chord. In measure 51, A7b9b13 (A-Bb-Db-E-F-G), Martino uses the Bb melodic minor to develop the melody. Based on this understanding, he focuses on the A7alt chord, using a minor substitution derived from a minor second above the root to emphasize the tension and set up a tension-and-release effect. In measure 52, Martino employs F major seventh materials in the context of a D minor seventh chord, a hallmark of his distinctive musical style. However, F major sixth can be interpreted as D minor seventh, allowing the sound of F major seventh (E-F-A-C) to be approached from a D minor ninth (D-F-A-C-E) perspective.

Example 4.15 “Just Friends,” mm. 49-52

In measure 131 (Example 4.16), Martino uses a descending G Dorian line - G, F, E, D - over the E minor seventh flat fifth chord and employs the notes Db, Bb, G, and Ab (with Ab functioning as a passing tone into the next measure) over the A7alt chord, collectively forming Bb minor materials. These substitution ideas align with the theoretical concepts discussed in Chapter 2 regarding Pat Martino's approach.

Example 4.16 “Just Friends,” mm. 131

4.1.5 Special Techniques Analysis

Martino is highly skilled at using chord tones to create double-stop rhythmic lines, a key element of his personal playing style. In mm. 105-107 (Example 4.17), Martino continues to use the double-stops technique with chord tones, incorporating rhythmic variation. In measure 108, over the Eb7 chord, he once again employs the idea of Bb minor substitution, then further develops this motif, driving the emotional intensity of the piece.

Example 4.17 “Just Friends,” mm. 105-108

Martino is also highly adept at using the guitar's unique capabilities to apply stairway chromatic sequencing techniques. In measure 117 (Example 4.18), he uses these techniques to create a sequence, enabling a smooth chromatic flow, which effectively resolves the tension.

Example 4.18 “Just Friends,” mm. 117

In measures 65-66 (Example 4.19), Martino employs the economic picking technique throughout the chord progression. He begins by playing a G minor seventh arpeggio, embellishing it with passing tones and using octave displacement to enhance the descending G Dorian scale. He continues to use G minor materials over the C7 chord, further confirming that minor substitution is a consistent element of his early performance approach. Similar passages can be observed in mm. 79-80 (Example 4.20) and 113-114 (Example 4.21). However, on beats three and four of measure 114, Martino uses neighbor tones to add another layer of melodic sophistication to his phrasing.

Example 4.18 shows a musical staff starting at measure 65. The first chord is Gm7, and the second is C7. The melody is a descending G Dorian scale. Annotations include: 'Gm7' above the first chord, 'Descending G Dorian Scale' above the scale line, 'G minor Arpeggio seventh' below the first measure, 'PT' (Passing Tone) with an upward arrow pointing to the second measure, 'Octave Displacement' with an upward arrow pointing to the third measure, and '(Economic Picking)' in a bracket below the first two measures.

Example 4.19 “Just Friends,” mm. 65-66

Example 4.19 shows a musical staff starting at measure 79. The first chord is Abm7, and the second is Db7. The melody is a descending Ab Dorian scale. Annotations include: 'Abm7' above the first chord, 'Descending Ab Dorian Scale' above the scale line, 'Ab minor Arpeggio seventh' below the first measure, 'PT' (Passing Tone) with an upward arrow pointing to the second measure, 'Octave Displacement' with an upward arrow pointing to the third measure, and '(Economic Picking)' in a bracket below the first two measures.

Example 4.20 “Just Friends,” mm. 79-80

Example 4.20 shows a musical staff starting at measure 113. The first chord is Gm7, and the second is C7. The melody is a descending G Dorian scale. Annotations include: 'Gm7' above the first chord, 'Descending G Dorian Scale' above the scale line, 'G minor Arpeggio seventh' below the first measure, 'PT' (Passing Tone) with an upward arrow pointing to the second measure, 'Octave Displacement' with an upward arrow pointing to the third measure, and '(Economic Picking)' in a bracket below the first two measures. Additionally, 'NT NT' (Neighbor Tones) are indicated above the final two notes of the scale.

Example 4.21 “Just Friends,” mm. 113-114

The solo in “Just Friends” is a prime example of Pat Martino’s improvisational style. In his three-chorus solo, Martino showcases his unique expressive qualities as an emerging musician in his early twenties. Analysis of this solo from the perspectives of melodic construction, rhythm, harmony, and embellishment reveals sequences, substitutions, upper structure, anticipations, and more, fully demonstrating his distinctive approach to performance. These insights are valuable for tracking Martino’s evolving vocabulary and performance techniques across different periods of his career, providing a comprehensive reference for understanding his stylistic transitions over time.

4.2 “Joyous Lake” Analysis

4.2.1 Background Information

“Joyous Lake” (1977) is a jazz fusion composition by Pat Martino, set in the key of G major, with a 250bpm tempo, 6/4 polyrhythmic Bossa nova feel, and 62-measure AABB form.

The composition is steeped in a sense of mystery, and its fusion character showcases the diversity of Martino’s musical output. This analysis explores Martino’s distinctive personal style and artistic versatility on the basis of a 72-measure transcription, highlighting the most representative segments for detailed discussion and presentation.

Table 4.2 Structure of “Joyous Lake”

Measure	[1-62]	[63-134]	[134-154]	[155-226]	[227-301]
Time Span	0: 00-1: 29	1: 30-3: 13	3: 14-3: 43	3: 44-5: 27	5: 28-7: 39
	Head in	Guitar solo (used for analysis)	To melody B section as Interlude	Ep solo	Head out
Number of measures	62 measures	72 measures	20 measures	72 measures	75measures

4.2.2 Melodic Construction Analysis

In measures 79-82 (Example 4.22), Martino employs a rhythmic motif over the A7 chord, using it as the basis for developing his phrase. Most of the notes are centered around E, reflecting his characteristic approach to creating emotional release. In measure 82, Martino introduces a descending E Dorian idea on the fourth beat, which leads into the subsequent passionate passage. This entire approach aligns with his use of E minor materials over the A7 chord.

Example 4.22 “Joyous Lake,” mm. 79-82

In measure 104 (Example 4.23), Martino uses octave displacement over the D minor seventh chord, raising the note E by an octave to expand the melodic range and enhance tension. Following this, the Eb appears on the downbeat, creating an “outside” sound before reverting to the chord tones C and D, thereby completing the release of tension. In the third beat, Martino connects the D to the root note C of the next chord via a half-step approach, continuing with a chromatic descent to reach the chord tone Bb of the C7sus4 chord. Subsequently, the D, F, and A notes form a D minor upper structure triad, generating an exciting sense of harmonic tension.

Example 4.23 “Joyous Lake,” mm. 104

In measures 105-108 (Example 4.24), Martino uses the same notes and rhythmic pattern throughout the entire chord progression, a technique reminiscent of his blues influence. This approach serves to heighten the audience’s emotional response,

drawing on Martino’s early experiences performing blues. A similar passage can be found in measures 129-131 (Example 4.25).

Example 4.24 “Joyous Lake,” mm. 105-108

Example 4.25 “Joyous Lake,” mm. 129-131

In measure 111 (Example 4.26), Martino employs the technique of enclosure, centering around the notes B and G to develop the phrase. This is one of the most frequently occurring motifs in his career, and mastering the use of enclosure is essential for effectively emulating Martino’s characteristic sound.

Example 4.26 “Joyous Lake,” mm. 111

In measure 115 (Example 4.27), Martino centers his playing around the notes F#, A, E, and G, embellishing these notes with passing tones, neighboring tones, and chromatic approaches. On the final beat, he employs a quartal interval to complete the measure’s phrasing, adding depth to the overall interpretation.

Example 4.27 “Joyous Lake,” mm. 115

4.2.3 Rhythmic Analysis

In measure 76 (Example 4.28), Martino uses an ascending A Mixolydian scale. In the first two beats of measure 77, he uses superimposed metric modulation, incorporating a quintuplet to create a sense of rhythmic overlap and complexity. On the final beat, he uses a triplet rhythm combined with a descending A Mixolydian scale to resolve to the root note in measure 78. For Martino, the A Mixolydian scale is often understood from an E Dorian perspective.

76 A7

Ascending A Mixolydian scale

Descending A Mixolydian scale

5 3

Superimposed Metric Modulation

Example 4.28 “Joyous Lake,” mm. 76-78

Martino begins his solo in measure 98 (Example 4.29) by focusing on the note D and the A7 chord tones during the first two beats. He then introduces a Bb quartal harmony starting on the third beat, creating an “outside” sound with a quartal interval. Starting from the fifth beat, he uses the bopping-the-top technique to incorporate the notes Eb and C into the Bb quartal harmony, disrupting the original meter and producing a sense of rhythmic overlap. By the fourth beat of measure 99, he resolves back to the tension and chord tones of the A7 chord, bringing the phrase to a cohesive conclusion.

98 A7

Bopping the Top

#11 b3

9 b7 13 5 R

P4 P4 P4

Bb Quartal Harmony

Example 4.29 “Joyous Lake,” mm. 98-99

In measures 121-123 (Example 4.30), Martino uses rhythmic displacement, starting four consecutive eighth notes at different beats across measures, creating a fresh rhythmic stimulus and adding new layers of interest to the phrasing.

Example 4.30 “Joyous Lake,” mm. 121-123

Martino maintains rhythmic density throughout measures 82-84 (Example 4.31), presenting a challenge for both himself and the audience. This intense and passionate style of playing has always been a significant contributor to Martino’s reputation in the jazz world as a dynamic performer.

Example 4.31 “Joyous Lake,” mm. 82-84

4.2.4 Harmonic Analysis

In measure 64 (Example 4.32), Martino begins his solo by using rests and the chord tones G and E, followed by chromatic movement leading into measure 65. Over the A7 chord, he employs an A minor pentatonic approach combined with quartal intervals.

Example 4.32 “Joyous Lake,” mm. 64-65

In measure 69 (Example 4.33), Martino uses a triadic approach combined with a descending A Mixolydian scale. In the next two measures, he incorporates a G major seventh (G, B, D, F \sharp) polychord concept. As discussed in Chapter 2, A7 can be approached using materials related to E minor, and G major seventh can be viewed as an alternative variation of E minor. Thus, G major seventh materials can be applied over the A7 chord. Martino likely interprets G major seventh from the perspective of E minor ninth (E, G, B, D, F \sharp).

69 A7 A major triad A Mixolydian A7 G major seventh materials A7

5 11 3 9 R b7 b7 9 11 13 R b7 5 P4

Example 4.33 “Joyous Lake,” mm. 69-71

In measure 86 (Example 4.34), over the A7 chord, Martino employs a G major seventh (G, B, D, F \sharp) polychord concept, although he tends to interpret this from the perspective of E minor ninth (E, G, B, D, F \sharp). Subsequently, over the A7alt chord, he uses G minor materials, which aligns with his multiple substitution approach, demonstrating its practical application in Martino’s playing.

86 A7 G major seventh materials A7(alt) G minor materials

Example 4.34 “Joyous Lake,” mm. 86

In measure 89 (Example 4.35), Martino uses G major seventh (G, B, D, F \sharp) materials over the A minor thirteenth chord. This approach represents a generalized improvisational concept in which he views A minor seventh as the ii chord of G major, allowing him to use G-major-related materials and passing tone (F). This concept is particularly significant, as Martino frequently used it after his surgery to create melodic expressions. In measure 90, over the A7alt chord, the idea from the previous measure continues until the first beat, ensuring continuity, Martino then employs A7alt chord

tones and Bb melodic minor materials, further supporting the multiple substitution technique discussed in Chapter 2.

Example 4.35 “Joyous Lake,” mm. 89-90

In measure 93 (Example 4.36), Martino uses D minor materials over the B minor seventh flat fifth chord, recognizing that B minor seventh flat fifth is equivalent to D minor sixth, a concept that is deeply ingrained in his approach throughout his career, while incorporating chromatic embellishments to add nuance to the melodic line. In measure 94, over the E7alt chord, Martino employs F minor major ninth (F, Ab, C, E, G) materials, which aligns with the substitution concepts of dissonant dominant chords discussed in Chapter 2.

Example 4.36 “Joyous Lake,” mm. 93-94

In measure 101 (Example 4.37), Martino employs quartal harmony on both A and D. This use of quartal voicings represents a relatively new direction in his playing at this point in his career, signaling Martino’s exploration of new sonic possibilities and stylistic elements that differentiate his approach from that on *El Hombre*.

Example 4.37 “Joyous Lake,” mm. 101

4.2.5 Special Techniques Analysis

In measure 127 (Example 4.38), Martino employs the double-stop technique on the guitar over the A7 chord, creating rhythmic lines. In the first two beats of this measure, he introduces quarter-note triplets, producing a sense of rhythmic overlap a distinctive feature of his playing style.

127

Double-Stops

Superimposed Metric Modulation

Example 4.38 “Joyous Lake,” mm. 127

The solo in “Joyous Lake” is an important example of Pat Martino’s improvisational style in the jazz fusion genre. In this performance, Martino showcases his unique expressiveness and versatility, effectively demonstrating the complexity and depth of his musical output. This analysis has revealed a wide range of techniques, including motivic development, octave displacement, bopping the top, and harmonic substitutions, highlighting his distinctive approach to creating tension and release. His use of quartal harmony also underscores his exploration of new harmonic concepts during this period. This analysis provides valuable insights into Martino’s evolving musical vocabulary and performance techniques, serving as a comprehensive reference for understanding his stylistic evolution.

4.3 “Turnpike” Analysis

4.3.1 Background Information

“Turnpike” is a hard bop composition by Pat Martino, featured on his 1989 album *The Return*. This original work exemplifies Martino’s innovative approach to harmony and melody, showcasing his unique artistry within the jazz idiom. Typically performed at a brisk 250 bpm in an up-tempo swing style, the piece is written in 4/4 time and deliberately eschews a fixed key center, demonstrating Martino’s masterful command of tonal ambiguity. Its 64-measure AABC form challenges both performers and listeners with its intricate, high-velocity melodic lines and driving energy. “Turnpike” stands as a testament to Martino’s technical brilliance and creative depth,

offering a demanding yet rewarding experience that continues to captivate musicians and audiences alike.

The 1995 live performance of “Turnpike” at The Knitting Factory in New York City reveals the evolution of Martino’s playing style before and after his surgery, highlighting essential changes in his technique. These developments are invaluable for a comprehensive understanding of Martino’s artistry and are integral to exploring his stylistic transformation. The following sections will comprehensively analyze a 65-measure transcription, highlighting the most representative segments for detailed discussion and presentation.

Table 4.3 Structure of “Turnpike”

Measure	[1-64]	[65-256]	[257-448]	[449-512]	[513-576]	[577-640]
Time Span	0: 00- 1: 04	1: 05- 4: 14	4: 15- 7: 30	7: 31- 8: 31	8: 32- 9: 36	9: 37- 10: 43
	Head in	Guitar solo (used for analysis)	Piano solo	Guitar Trade 8	Guitar solo	Head out
Number of measures	64 measures	192 measures	192 measures	64 measures	64 measures	64 measures

4.3.2 Melodic Construction Analysis

In measure 77 (Example 4.39), over the F/G chord, Martino employs the indirect resolution technique to ornament the target note F, while utilizing the enclosure technique around the note C. In measure 78 (Example 4.40), over the same F/G chord, Martino uses a G7#11 arpeggio as the melodic framework, incorporating the chromatic note F# as an embellishment to create a Mixolydian b7 color. At the end of this measure, he applies the neighbor tone technique on F to seamlessly connect into the following measure. In measure 79, Martino constructs the melody using the G7sus arpeggio and chord tones related to G7. However, Martino tends to conceptualize the F/G chord as G7sus, visualizing the melodic framework from the perspective of minor intervals above

the root note D, a perfect fifth above G. This approach highlights his unique perspective in navigating and visualizing harmonic structures.

Example 4.39 “Turnpike,” mm. 77

Example 4.40 “Turnpike,” mm. 78-79

In measure 86 (Example 4.41), over the Ab9 chord, Martino employs octave displacement to ornament a Gb major seventh arpeggio, using Eb on the fourth beat as the target note through indirect resolution. However, Martino’s conceptual approach remains rooted in viewing Gb major seventh through the lens of Eb minor ninth, reflecting his distinctive harmonic perspective. In measure 87, Martino uses Ab as a pivot point, embellishing the melodic line. On the fourth beat, he once again uses indirect resolution to transition to the next measure, targeting the note Gb. In measure 88, Martino applies the double chromatic approach to the note Eb, a reflection of his concept of playing minor materials based on a perfect fifth above the root (here, Ab7). This approach highlights Martino’s ability to integrate advanced chromatic techniques into his melodic construction, further enriching the harmonic context.

Example 4.41 “Turnpike,” mm. 86-88

In measures 93-94 (Example 4.42), over the F/G chord, Martino uses a chromatic scale to connect to the target note D, initiating an ascending G Mixolydian scale that leads into the first note A of the next measure. He then incorporates another

ascending chromatic scale, culminating on the third beat with a D minor 5 b3 2 1 digital pattern, effectively completing the melodic interpretation with precision and fluidity.

93 F/G

Target

5 13 b7 R 9 #9 3 11

Chromatic scale G Mixolydian scale ascending Chromatic scale Dminor5 b3 2 1 pattern

Example 4.42 “Turnpike,” mm. 93-94

In measure 95 (Example 4.43), over the F/G chord, Martino employs his signature stairway chromaticism to connect to the chord’s third, B. On the second half of the third beat, he uses a combination of hammer-ons and pull-offs along with double-stops to transition smoothly into the next measure. In measure 96, Martino embellishes an F major seventh arpeggio using octave displacement, adding a unique flair to the arpeggio. However, Martino’s conceptual framework leans more toward visualizing this idea through a D minor ninth arpeggio.

95 F/G

Stairway Chromaticism

3

Octave Displacement

F Major seventh Arpeggio

Target Double-Stops

b7 9

Example 4.43 “Turnpike,” mm. 95-96

4.3.3 Rhythmic Analysis

In measure 95 (Example 4.44), over the Gb major seventh / Bb chord, Martino employs syncopation to create a rhythmic buffer, adding an element of playfulness to the performance while preparing for the next extended linear passage. This technique, a hallmark of his style throughout his career, reflects Martino’s deep connection to rhythm. In a masterclass, Martino once remarked that rhythm, for him, is akin to dancing, underscoring the integral role it plays in his musical expression.

Example 4.44 “Turnpike,” mm. 89

In measures 76-77 (Example 4.45), over the D7#9 chord, Martino performs an Eb7sus arpeggio, a minor second above the chord root. This approach stems from Martino’s practice of utilizing Eb minor materials to construct a D altered sound. Starting on the third beat, Martino applies rhythmic displacement to complete the rhythmic framework of the remaining notes. In measure 77, Martino targets F using indirect resolution, while on the third beat, he employs enclosure around C, adding a nuanced embellishment to the melodic line. This interplay of harmonic and rhythmic techniques exemplifies Martino’s mastery of melodic construction.

Example 4.45 “Turnpike,” mm. 76-77

In measures 101-108 (Example 4.46), Martino demonstrates his enduring preference for rhythmic density, showcasing the unpredictable and passionate qualities characteristic of his hard-bop playing style. Remarkably, this dynamic and intricate approach to performance remains entirely unaffected by his surgery, reaffirming the unshakable significance of his style and techniques in the jazz guitar world.

101 $Dm7^{b9}/E$

105

Example 4.46 “Turnpike,” mm. 101-108

4.3.4 Harmonic Analysis

In measures 105-106 (Example 4.47), over the D minor seventh flat fifth / E chord, Martino incorporates a combination of outside notes and select chord tones to heighten the tension in his performance. The first step in this approach is to master Martino’s octave displacement chromatic technique across different strings. The second step is to select a core note and treat the four directions on the guitar neck as North, South, East, and West. Starting near the core note, the player should develop an “outside” melody by combining its unique chromatic technique from various directions, without restriction.⁴⁵ In measure 105, during the first two beats, Martino develops an “outside” line with A as the core note. In the last two beats, he shifts to C as the core note, continuing the “outside” development. In measure 106, for the first two beats, Martino uses G as the core note to develop an “outside” line, and for the last two beats, he shifts to A^b as the core note, again developing the “outside” approach. These measures also subtly indicate Martino’s exploration of outside concepts, showcasing his innovative approach to harmonic and rhythmic experimentation.

$Dm7^{b9}/E$

105

$b9$ R 7 5

$b5$

3

11 $b13$ 13

$b5$ $b7$ 3

Example 4.47 “Turnpike,” mm. 105-106

In measures 65-67 (Example 4.48), over the E^b major seventh / G chord, Martino combines E^b major scale with the 1 9 3 5 digital pattern to craft his melodic

⁴⁵ Aarson, Debble, and Martino, *Creative Force*

line. This is followed by a brief pause using the chord tones of a C minor triad. However, from Martino’s perspective, the harmonic material is consistently categorized and approached as C minor rather than being derived from the Eb major seventh chord. This conceptual distinction, central to Martino’s methodology, is a defining characteristic of his playing style and permeates his entire career.

Example 4.48 “Turnpike,” mm. 65-67

In measure 69 (Example 4.49), over the Ab9 chord, Martino constructs his melody using an Eb minor major ninth arpeggio, creating an Ab Lydian b7 sound. In measure 72 (Example 4.50), Martino employs a Gb major triad, subtly infusing chromatic embellishments, to build a melody over the Ab9 chord. Gb major corresponds to Eb minor, where Eb serves as the perfect fifth extension above Ab9. This demonstrates Martino’s multifaceted approach to harmonic interpretation. In measure 74 (Example 4.51), Martino uses Eb minor materials to construct a melody over the Gb major seventh / Bb chord, imparting a Gb Lydian tonal color to the passage. In measure 92 (Example 4.52), over the D7#9 chord, Martino combines Eb minor materials with G minor pentatonic descending, employing minor materials a minor second above the chord to produce a D altered sound. While the harmonic progression has yet to resolve to G minor seventh, Martino anticipates the shift by using G minor materials to establish a temporary tonal center. This approach marks a notable departure from his earlier methods, further highlighting his evolving conceptual framework.

Example 4.49 “Turnpike,” mm. 69

Example 4.50 “Turnpike,” mm. 72

Example 4.51 “Turnpike,” mm. 74

Example 4.52 “Turnpike,” mm. 92

In measures 107-108 (Example 4.53), over the D minor seventh flat fifth chord, Martino employs quartal intervals and harmony as the foundation for his melodic construction. Additionally, he incorporates perfect fifths and minor sixths to enhance the musical texture and add a layer of rhythmic and harmonic interest. This approach echoes his pre-surgery exploration of quartal harmony, as prominently featured in “Joyous Lake,” further showcasing his consistent fascination with this technique throughout his career.

Example 4.53 “Turnpike,” mm. 107-108

4.3.5 Special Techniques Analysis

In measures 122-123 (Example 4.54), Martino uses an Ab major triad arpeggio as the basis for his melodic line. He then employs his signature double-stops

to ornament the third (Gb) and fifth (Bb) of Eb minor, seamlessly connecting the Gb major seventh / Bb and A7 chords. This approach simultaneously introduces a tense and stimulating A altered (Aalt) auditory effect over the A7 chord, showcasing Martino’s ability to create harmonic tension while maintaining melodic coherence.

Example 4.54 “Turnpike,” mm. 122-123

In measure 104 (Example 4.55), Martino employs his signature stairway chromaticism to navigate fretboard positions. On the third beat, he uses the chromatic approach technique to ornament E, introducing the 11th (G) to enhance the harmonic texture. Together, these elements create the distinct auditory color of D Locrian #2, exemplifying Martino’s masterful integration of chromaticism and modal nuances.

Example 4.55 “Turnpike,” mm. 104

This rendition of “Turnpike” showcases Pat Martino’s continued adherence to his pre-surgery playing habits, both technically and theoretically. Despite undergoing surgery, his approach to musical thought remained largely intact. Instead of significant changes in his performance philosophy, the experience prompted a profound introspection, leading Martino to relearn, expand, and further explore the depths of music with renewed perspective and creativity.

4.4 “Think Tank” Analysis

4.4.1 Background Information

“Think Tank” is a post-bop composition by Pat Martino created in 2003. The piece highlights Martino’s ingenuity in both harmony and melody, serving as one of his most profound tributes to John Coltrane. It also reflects the cherished memories of their friendship, which had a lasting impact on Martino’s artistic journey. Performed in a medium-up swing style at 165 bpm, “Think Tank” is written in 4/4 time and deliberately avoids a fixed key center, allowing for harmonic fluidity and exploration. Its intricate 80-measure ABCDB structure offers a richly layered and immersive musical experience, challenging performers while deeply engaging listeners. This composition stands as a testament to Martino’s ability to blend technical sophistication with heartfelt homage, honoring Coltrane’s legacy while carving out a unique space in the post-bop tradition.

Martino’s personal letter system aligns seamlessly with his post-bop philosophy, transcending conventional musical boundaries. This approach provides valuable insights into his playing system, offering a deeper understanding of his artistic framework. The following sections will provide a comprehensive analysis of a 89-measure transcription, highlighting the most representative segments for detailed discussion and presentation.

Table 4.4 Structure of “Think Tank”

Measure	[1-16]	[17-36]	[37-116]	[117-196]
Time Span	0: 00-0: 21	0: 22-0: 49	0: 50-2: 47	2: 48-4: 43
	[Intro] Drum solo 16 measures	[Intro] Piano, Bass and Drum	Head in	Guitar solo (used for analysis)
Number of measures	16 measures	20 measures	80 measures	80 measures
Measure	[197-204]	[205-252]	[253-296]	[297-392]
Time Span	4: 44-4: 55	4: 56-7: 10	7: 11-9: 44	9: 45-12: 09
	Guitar solo Interlude	Piano solo	Sax solo	Head out

Number of measures	8 measures	48 measures	44 measures	96 measures
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4.4.2 Melodic Construction Analysis

In measures 125-126 (Example 4.56), Martino employs C minor materials to navigate the B7alt chord. In measure 125, he continues the eighth-note motif from the previous measure, transitions into triplets, and introduces sixteenth notes starting on the third beat. This strategic use of double time creates the illusion of varying note speeds, adding rhythmic complexity and melodic intrigue. On the upbeat of the fourth beat, he skillfully employs indirect resolution to transition into the following measure. In measure 126, Martino begins the first beat with an ascending C Dorian scale, followed by the application of the pivot tones technique on the second beat to develop the melody further. On the third beat, he incorporates an F7 arpeggio, extending the melodic line and maintaining continuity within his improvisational framework.

Example 4.56 “Think Tank,” mm. 125-126

In measure 150 (Example 4.57), Martino employs Eb minor materials against the harmonic backdrop of A minor seventh, creating an intense and stimulating sound. Within this framework, he first uses a double chromatic approach to connect to the root note Eb. He then initiates a descending line using the Eb Dorian scale, transitioning through G and connecting to Gb before resolving to the target note F via indirect resolution.

Example 4.57 “Think Tank,” mm. 150

In measures 155-156 (Example 4.58), Martino employs intervallic transformation technique, developing the melody through a persistent rhythmic motif while varying the pitch content. The materials incorporates arpeggios derived from Db seventh (omit3), C sus fourth, C# minor sixth, G# minor seventh, and Eb minor ninth, along with chromatic passing tones, all structured around a triplet rhythmic pattern that drives the melodic progression. In the final two beats of the passage, Martino uses a descending C minor scale starting from the Eb note down to the target note C, and then ascends using a Db minor scale from Db to the target note E, adding complexity and depth to the melodic line.

Example 4.58 “Think Tank,” mm. 155-156

In measures 179-180 (Example 4.59), Martino adheres to the harmonic framework of the Am chord. Martino begins measure 179 with an ascending A Dorian scale starting from B, incorporating the b5 to evoke a bluesy sound. On the upbeat of the second beat, he employs indirect resolution to resolve to the 13th (F#) on the third beat. Continuing upward, he uses the A melodic minor scale, reaching D before again applying the indirect resolution technique to land on C on the second half of the fourth beat. He then uses E as a connecting note to transition smoothly into the next measure.

In measure 180, Martino uses an E minor seventh arpeggio and incorporates diatonic tones from A natural minor, effectively concluding the melodic line while maintaining cohesion with the harmonic context.

Example 4.59 “Think Tank,” mm. 179-180

4.4.3 Rhythmic Analysis

In measure 122 (Example 4.60), Martino constructs the melody on the notes C and A combined with triplets as the primary motif. He makes use of bopping the top technique to further creates a sense of rhythmic feeling, adding complexity to the passage. A similar approach is observed in measure 148 (Example 4.61), exemplifying one of Martino’s signature stylistic traits. This recurring technique underscores his innovative approach to rhythm and phrasing, making it a hallmark of his playing style.

Example 4.60 “Think Tank,” mm. 122-123

Example 4.61 “Think Tank,” mm. 148

In measures 129-131 (Example 4.62), over the A minor seventh chord, Martino employs A minor seventh arpeggios in a rapid sixteenth-note run, seamlessly integrating rests, syncopation, and chord tones as breathing spaces within the melodic line. This strategic use of phrasing not only alleviates potential auditory fatigue caused

by high-density passages but also enhances the overall melodic expressiveness of the solo, contributing to a more dynamic and engaging performance.

Example 4.62 “Think Tank,” mm. 129-131

In measures 192-193 (Example 4.63), Martino begins his melodic construction using G# as a pivot note, bopping the top to create a counter-rhythm to the underlying pulse. Over the E7alt chord, he uses C minor materials, while under the A minor seventh chord, he incorporates chord tones and tension from Gb major materials, producing an intensely outside sound. This passage delivers a highly stimulating auditory experience, showcasing Martino’s masterful ability to push harmonic and rhythmic boundaries while maintaining a cohesive and dynamic melodic flow.

Example 4.63 “Think Tank,” mm. 192-193

In measures 203-204 (Example 4.64), Martino employs rhythmic subdivision, creating the illusion of fluctuating melodic speed. He integrates Economic Picking to execute sweeping motions across the triads of Bb major, A major, Ab major, G major, and Gb major, blending elements reminiscent of rock guitar techniques. The frequent shifts between outside and inside tonalities further enhance the aggressive and dynamic character of the passage. Finally, in measure 204, Martino resolves the tension by returning to chord tones on the third and fourth beats, providing a gradual sense of release and balance to the performance.

Example 4.64 “Think Tank,” mm. 203-204

4.4.4 Harmonic Analysis

In measure 127 (Example 4.65), over the E7alt chord, Martino begins the melodic line with the tonic A minor triad, establishing a clear and grounded opening. On the upbeat of the fourth beat, he employs a sixteenth-note passing tone to seamlessly connect to the following measure. In measure 128, still over the E7alt chord, Martino uses an Ab minor eleventh arpeggio to outline an outside melody, adding harmonic tension and depth to the improvisation. This approach highlights Martino’s ability to blend traditional and adventurous harmonic elements, crafting compelling and unpredictable lines.

Example 4.65 “Think Tank,” mm. 127-128

In measure 133 (Example 4.66), over the A minor seventh chord, Martino employs a double chromatic approach on the third beat to resolve to the note Db, initiating a descending Db Dorian scale. In measure 134, Martino continues to use the Double Chromatic Approach, once again targeting Db and descending through the Db Dorian scale. On the upbeat of the third beat, he incorporates E as a pivot note, effectively completing the melodic construction. The entire melodic line integrates Db minor materials along with chord tones, maintaining a compelling interplay between outside and inside tonalities, ultimately achieving a satisfying sense of resolution. This balance showcases Martino’s masterful control over harmonic tension and release.

Example 4.66 “Think Tank,” mm. 133-134

Over the A minor seventh add eleventh chord in measure 136 (Example 4.67), Martino constructs an outside melody based on the chord tones of Gb major add ninth and a triplet rhythmic pattern. He resolves the tension on the fourth beat by returning to the original tonal center of A minor seventh, seamlessly blending the outside exploration with a satisfying resolution to the harmonic framework.

Example 4.67 “Think Tank,” mm. 136

In measure 141 (Example 4.68), over the B7alt chord, Martino employs a C minor eleventh arpeggio combined with a descending C Dorian scale to develop the melody. This approach reflects a return to his characteristic harmonic preferences, aligning with his established improvisational style while maintaining a cohesive melodic structure.

Example 4.68 “Think Tank,” mm. 141

4.4.5 Special Techniques Analysis

In measure 181 (Example 4.69), over the A minor seventh add eleventh chord, Martino incorporates the blues note Eb alongside the fifth E, utilizing the slide technique and double-stops to construct the melody. The resulting melodic line exudes a distinctly bluesy character, showcasing one of Martino’s most iconic and recognizable stylistic elements. This passage highlights his ability to seamlessly integrate blues influences into his jazz improvisation, creating a sound that is uniquely his own.

Example 4.69 “Think Tank,” mm. 181-182

In measure 186 (Example 4.70), over the A minor seventh add eleventh chord, Martino employs open string and string pull-off techniques to drive the emotional intensity of the performance. Additionally, he uses four-note groupings to disrupt the rhythmic perception of the septuplets, creating an overlay of rhythmic pulses – a hallmark application of bopping the top. The melody transitions from the original triplet feel to the higher density of septuplet phrases, exemplifying the classic use of superimposed metric modulation. This passage showcases Martino’s mastery in blending rhythmic innovation with technical precision, resulting in a dynamic and compelling improvisational line.

Example 4.70 “Think Tank,” mm. 186-187

In measures 184–185 (Example 4.71), Martino constructs the melodic line over the A minor seventh add eleventh chord with G minor materials, which share significant common tones with the original A minor tonal center, resulting in a subtle outside sound that blends seamlessly with the harmonic framework. Beginning with quarter notes, he applies rhythmic subdivision to create rhythmic variation. Martino further uses economic picking and stairway chromaticism to craft a fluid and dynamic interpretation of the melody, showcasing his technical mastery and innovative approach to phrasing.

Example 4.71 “Think Tank,” mm. 184-185

The 1995 rendition of “Turnpike” marks the beginning of Martino’s exploration into and subtle departure from traditional harmonic frameworks. This evolution had reached its apex by the time of “Think Tank,” with Martino incorporating outside harmonic concepts that were totally new to his music. While the performance diverges significantly from conventional jazz harmonies, it retains the essence of his earlier stylistic habits, reflecting a deep connection to his roots. This marked a groundbreaking chapter in his career, symbolizing the emergence of his post-bop style and his challenge to traditional jazz harmony. It was during this period that discussions of his past associations with Coltrane resurfaced, as audiences and critics alike began to feel Coltrane’s influence reverberating through Martino’s music once again. This connection underscored the profound and enduring impact Coltrane had on Martino’s artistic journey, drawing listeners into a renewed appreciation of his innovative approach.

4.5 “Lean Years” Analysis

4.5.1 Background

“Lean Years” is a hard bop composition by Pat Martino created in 1967. Typically performed at a brisk 240 bpm in an up-tempo swing style, the piece is written in 4/4 time and deliberately avoids a fixed key center. It’s a 64-measure AABC structure departs from the conventional 32-measure form, exemplifying Martino’s innovative approach to composition. The piece’s driving rhythm and rapid tempo are hallmarks of the hard bop style, yet it also carries a profound emotional depth, reflecting the formative influence of Martino’s early experiences. “Lean Years” is a testament to his ability to blend technical mastery with deeply personal expression, capturing the essence of a pivotal period in his artistic development.

I have selected the version of “Lean Years” from the album *Undeniable: Live at Blues Alley* (2011). The band members include Tony Monaco on organ, Jeff Tain Watts on drums, and Eric Alexander on saxophone. The following sections will provide a comprehensive analysis of a 128-measure transcription, highlighting the most representative segments for detailed discussion and presentation.

Table 4.5 Structure of “Lean Years”

Measure	[1-64]	[65-256]	[257-320]	[321-384]	[385-448]
Time Span	0: 00- 1: 08	1: 09- 4: 14	4: 15- 5: 18	5: 19- 6: 21	6: 22- 7: 37
	Head in	Guitar solo (used for analysis)	Sax solo	Organ solo	Head out
Number of measures	64 measures	192 measures	64 measures	64 measures	64 measures

4.5.2 Melodic Construction Analysis

Martino begins on the third beat of measure 80 (Example 4.72), over the D minor chord, using chord tones to connect seamlessly to the 13th (B) on the downbeat of the next measure. In measure 81, Martino applies indirect resolution on the second

beat to return to the note B and again on the fourth beat to transition to the B in the following measure. In measure 82, he incorporates chord tones on the second beat and follows with the E minor chord tones G and B, employing double-stops to further enrich the melodic texture. In measure 83, Martino repeats Motif 1 from the second to the fourth beat of measure 81. In measure 84, he applies the same concept to repeat Motif 2 from measure 82. In measure 85, Martino introduces variations to Motif 1 by employing intervallic transformation. Finally, in measure 86, he uses neighbor tones around the root note to conclude the passage, delivering a flawless and cohesive presentation of the entire example.

The musical notation for Example 4.72, "Lean Years," mm. 80-86, is presented in two staves. The first staff (measures 80-83) shows a D minor 9th chord (Dm9) with notes 5, b7, and 13. Motif 1 is defined as IR Target IR Target, and Motif 2 is defined as Double-Stops. The second staff (measures 84-86) shows a D minor 9th chord (Dm9) with notes b5, 5, R, b9, R, and 9. The notation includes annotations for Intervallic transformation and Repeat Motif 1.

Example 4.72 "Lean Years," mm. 80-86

In measure 87 (Example 4.73), Martino outlines the D minor ninth chord using its chord tones and tensions while incorporating the pedal tone technique to add depth and sustain the melody. In measure 88, over the D minor ninth chord, Martino begins on the upbeat of the first beat with a chromatic approach leading to the b3 (F) on the second beat. He continues by applying the same chromatic approach on the third beat to reach the 13 (B), and again on the upbeat of the fourth beat, connecting seamlessly to the following measure. In measure 89, over the C minor ninth chord, Martino uses a 5 b3 9 R digital pattern combined with the enclosure technique, effectively developing the melodic line and enhancing its harmonic complexity. These techniques demonstrate Martino's ability to blend advanced theoretical concepts with expressive phrasing, creating a cohesive and dynamic passage.

Example 4.73 “Lean Years,” mm. 87-89

In measure 94 (Example 4.74), Martino constructs the melody over the D minor ninth chord by combining chord tones and tensions, enhanced with indirect resolution to craft an expressive line. In measure 95, Martino employs quarter notes to introduce a brief moment of rest, providing a rhythmic and melodic pause that sets the stage for the next long, passionate linear phrase. This thoughtful use of space underscores his mastery in balancing intensity and phrasing within his improvisation.

Example 4.74 “Lean Years,” mm. 94-95

In measures 97-99 (Example 4.75), Martino constructs the melody using Eb minor ninth chord tones and the Eb Dorian bebop scale as the foundation. He further incorporates the chromatic embellishments and a pedal tone, blending these elements with the enclosure technique to ornament and enhance the melodic line. This combination of techniques results in a cohesive and richly textured phrase, showcasing Martino’s skillful integration of harmonic and melodic complexity.

Example 4.75 “Lean Years,” mm. 97-99

In measures 125-126 (Example 4.76), over the D minor ninth chord, Martino uses a descending D harmonic minor scale while incorporating E as a pedal tone to anchor the melody. He concludes the passage with a D minor major seventh arpeggio, creating a refined and cohesive melodic structure that highlights his precision and mastery of harmony.

125 D Harmonic minor scale descending Pivot note D minor major seventh

9 R 7 b13 5 9 11 b3 11 R 7 5

Example 4.76 “Lean Years,” mm. 125-126

In measures 161-162 (Example 4.77), over the Eb minor ninth chord, Martino constructs a two-measure melody by combining chord tones with the intervallic transformation technique. This approach showcases his ability to craft intricate and dynamic lines while maintaining harmonic coherence, exemplifying his innovative approach to melodic development.

161 Ebm9 Intervallic transformation

5 b3 9 R

Example 4.77 “Lean Years,” mm. 161-162

4.5.3 Rhythmic Analysis

In measures 105-107 (Example 4.78), Martino constructs a rhythmic motif based on chord tones and develops it further using the rhythmic displacement technique, placing the motif on different beats to create a sense of dynamic variation. This approach results in the construction of a cohesive and engaging two-measure melodic line, showcasing Martino’s mastery in blending harmonic structure with rhythmic innovation.

105 Dbm9 Rhythmic Displacement

9 b3 R 5

Example 4.78 “Lean Years,” mm. 105-107

In measure 124 (Example 4.79), Martino employs chord tones, rests, and syncopation to create a melodic breathing space, effectively setting the stage for the next high-density passage. This deliberate use of phrasing demonstrates his ability to balance intensity and space, ensuring a dynamic and engaging flow within his improvisation.

Example 4.79 “Lean Years,” mm. 124

In measures 72-76 (Example 4.80), the melodic line showcases Martino’s masterful use of rhythmic density, a defining element of his hard bop style. Even in the final stages of his life, his performances remained fiery and full of passion.

Example 4.80 “Lean Years,” mm. 72-76**4.5.4 Harmonic Analysis**

In measure 73 (Example 4.81), Martino begins the melodic line over the C minor ninth chord with a descending C minor pentatonic scale, introducing the distinct sound of an Eb major seventh arpeggio, a hallmark of his style. In measure 74, over the F9 chord, Martino incorporates chord tones while blending the #9, creating a dynamic tonal shift that adds the richness of F9 to the auditory palette.

Example 4.81 “Lean Years,” mm. 73-74

In measures 100-101 (Example 4.82), Martino develops the melodic line over the Eb minor ninth chord by incorporating a Gb major upper structure triad along with Eb minor ninth chord tones. This approach reflects a return to his foundational playing habits, blending harmonic structure with melodic fluidity.

Example 4.82 “Lean Years,” mm. 100-101

In measures 142-143 (Example 4.83), Martino constructs the melody over the D minor ninth chord using an F major ninth sharp fifth arpeggio combined with a descending D melodic minor scale. Notably, Martino approaches this passage from the perspective of D minor, seamlessly integrating these two techniques to shape the melodic line. This conceptual framework, rooted in his early playing philosophy, remained a defining aspect of his artistry even in his later years.

Example 4.83 “Lean Years,” mm. 142-143

In measure 156 (Example 4.84), over the A7b13 chord, Martino employs Bbminor materials, creating an A7alt sound that introduces tension and excitement. This heightened sense of harmonic instability enhances the resolution into the following

measure. This approach exemplifies Martino’s characteristic playing style, demonstrating a connection to the concepts outlined in Chapter Two and reinforcing the core principles of his improvisational philosophy.

Example 4.84 “Lean Years,” mm. 156

In measures 159-160 (Example 4.85), Martino approaches the D minor chord from its tonal perspective, beginning the melodic construction with an F major ninth sharp fifth arpeggio. He incorporates tensions, a double chromatic approach, and the b5 blues note Ab to complete the melodic idea. This blend of harmonic sophistication and blues influence highlights Martino’s ability to seamlessly integrate diverse elements into a cohesive and expressive improvisational framework.

Example 4.85 “Lean Years,” mm. 159-160

4.5.5 Special Techniques Analysis

In measures 78-79 (Example 4.86), Martino uses the tonal contrast between the second-string note E and the notes on the third string to create a distinct timbral variation. Additionally, he skillfully incorporates quarter notes to provide a rhythmic buffer, alleviating the potential fatigue caused by the preceding high-density passages. This thoughtful phrasing demonstrates Martino’s mastery in balancing intensity and musicality in his improvisations.

Example 4.86 “Lean Years,” mm. 78-79

In measures 90-91 (Example 4.87), Martino begins with a descending F Mixolydian scale, followed by a signature double-stops phrase highlighting the temporary tonic of Bb major ninth. This technique, which has appeared countless times throughout his performances, is essential for replicating his distinctive playing style. Its consistent use underscores how this approach became a defining feature of Martino’s artistry.

90 F⁹ 13 5 11 3

b13 13 b7 7 b5maj9 R b3 3

Double-Stops

F Mixolydian scale descending

Example 4.87 “Lean Years,” mm. 90-91

In measure 123 (Example 4.88), Martino incorporates slide technique to introduce the b3, seamlessly blending it with economic picking to create a hybrid major-minor tonal color. This type of phrase captivates listeners and has drawn countless fans to his distinctive sound.

123 b5maj9

R 5 11 3

Double-Stops

Example 4.88 “Lean Years,” mm. 123

In measures 128-130 (Example 4.89), Martino uses the notes F# and G, employing string bend technique to release emotional tension. He further creates a sense of rhythmic dislocation in the melodic phrasing by bopping the top. This distinctive technical approach, which persisted throughout his post-surgery career and into his later years, served as Martino’s musical equivalent of a resounding “yeah yeah” exclamation, connecting deeply with his audience and leaving a lasting impression.

Example 4.89 “Lean Years,” mm. 128-130

In measure 136 (Example 4.90), over the Dminor9 chord, Martino ascends the minor scale starting from D, reaching A on the third beat. He then employs his signature Stairway Chromaticism technique to connect seamlessly to the chord tone in the following measure. In measure 137, over the C minor ninth chord, Martino incorporates the concept of a Digital Pattern 5 b3 9 1 alongside a descending C minor scale starting from F, crafting a melodic line that blends precision with fluidity.

Example 4.90 “Lean Years,” mm. 136-137

In measures 145-146 (Example 4.91), Martino uses the open E string as a Pedal Tone, combined with Dorian scale tones to construct the melodic materials. This approach, in fact, permeates many measures throughout the piece, showcasing one of Martino’s hallmark techniques. This signature method, cherished by Martino, has been celebrated by audiences since “Sunny” and remains one of the most enduring and admired elements of his playing, a testament to its lasting impact on the musical world.

Example 4.91 “Lean Years,” mm. 145-146

In Martino’s later years, “Lean Years” remained one of his most frequently performed pieces, serving as a testament to decades of unparalleled technical mastery

and profound musical ideas. This rendition exemplifies the culmination of his artistry, a result shaped by history itself. It stands as an incredibly successful performance, fully encapsulating his lifelong dedication to jazz and the brilliance of his theoretical and technical contributions to the guitar. Departing from the exploratory and Coltrane-inspired “Think Tank,” “Lean Years” emerges as history’s ultimate gift. It not only celebrates Martino’s legacy as a jazz giant but also serves as a radiant reflection of his creative genius and enduring influence.

4.6 “Full House” Analysis

4.6.1 Background

“Full House” is a hard bop piece by Wes Montgomery composed in 1962. It is written in 3/4 time, set in the key of F minor, and follows a 64-measure AABA form. Pat Martino’s countless interpretations of this composition reflect his profound admiration for Wes Montgomery and serve as a testament to their deep and enduring friendship. These renditions not only honor Montgomery’s legacy but also highlight Martino’s ability to infuse his unique voice into this timeless masterpiece.

The version of “Full House” selected for this study is taken from the live performance by *The Pat Martino Organ Trio at Bielska Zadyмка Jazzowa* (2014). The band members include Pat Bianchi on organ and Carmen Intorre on drums. This song holds significant importance for understanding Pat Martino’s playing style during the final phase of his life. The following sections will provide a comprehensive analysis of a 136-measure transcription, highlighting the most representative segments for detailed discussion and presentation.

Table 4.6 Structure of “Full House”

Measure	[1-16]	[17-80]	[81-272]	[273-464]	[465-528]	[529-544]
Time Span	0: 00- 0: 17	0: 18- 1: 13	1: 14- 3: 53	3: 54- 6: 27	6: 28- 7: 19	7: 20- 7: 48
	Intro Organ,	Head in	Guitar solo	Organ solo	Head out	Outro

	Drum and Guitar		(used for analysis)			Organ, Drum and Guitar
Number of measures	16 measures	64 measures	192 measures	192 measures	64 measures	16 measures

4.6.2 Melodic Construction Analysis

In measures 83-85 (Example 4.92), Martino employs intervallic transformation, using the same rhythmic motif across different measures with varying pitch content. For the melody, Martino uses F minor materials over the F minor ninth and Bb13 chords, creating a cohesive and dynamic connection between the harmonic structures.

Example 4.92 “Full House,” mm. 83-85

In measures 103-104 (Example 4.93), Martino employs Bb minor materials to navigate both the G minor seventh flat fifth and C7#9 chords, maintaining a cohesive melodic structure. In measure 104, on the second beat, he uses Ab as a pedal tone, anchoring the melody and adding depth to its construction.

Example 4.93 “Full House,” mm. 103-104

In measures 105-106 (Example 4.94), Martino constructs Motif 1 and immediately repeats it, establishing a rhythmic and melodic foundation. In measures 107-109, he develops the melody using F minor ninth chord tones combined with tensions, incorporating Ab as a pedal tone to anchor the line. In measure 109, Martino

returns to Motif 1, seamlessly weaving it into the broader melodic framework. This approach showcases his ability to blend motivic consistency with harmonic and technical sophistication.

Example 4.94 “Full House,” mm. 105-109

In measures 129-131 (Example 4.95), Martino constructs the melodic framework using the chord tones of F minor ninth and Bb13, further enhancing the line with enclosure embellishments and double-stops. This combination of harmonic precision and stylistic ornamentation exemplifies Martino’s signature approach to melodic construction, blending technical finesse with expressive depth.

Example 4.95 “Full House,” mm. 129-131

4.6.3 Rhythmic Analysis

In measure 99 (Example 4.96), Martino uses F as a pivot note to construct the melody. In measure 100, he employs rhythmic displacement, shifting the rhythm from the previous measure to begin on the first beat. He further incorporates chromatic approaches to resolve back to the root note Bb, blending rhythmic innovation with harmonic resolution.

Example 4.96 “Full House,” mm. 99-100

In measures 147-148 (Example 4.97), Martino incorporates quarter notes and rests to create a melodic pause, providing a moment of rhythmic and dynamic relaxation. In measure 149, he introduces syncopation, adding rhythmic variation and complexity. This thoughtful interplay between rest and motion highlights Martino’s mastery in balancing phrasing and maintaining engagement within his improvisation.

Example 4.97 “Full House,” mm. 147-149

In measures 177-178 (Example 4.98), Martino employs Bb minor materials to construct the melody. In the last half-beat of measure 178, Martino uses the bopping-the-top technique, transitioning into measure 179. He then applies Ab major materials under the Ab major seventh chord, again integrating the bopping-the-top technique. This approach creates a counter-rhythm to the underlying pulse while maintaining a cohesive harmonic framework, highlighting Martino’s innovative use of both rhythmic and melodic elements in his improvisation.

Example 4.98 “Full House,” mm. 177-179

4.6.4 Harmonic Analysis

In measures 87-88 (Example 4.99), Martino constructs the melody over G minor seventh flat fifth using the chord tones of Db major ninth, while incorporating altered tones over C7#9. However, Martino consistently approaches these materials from the perspective of Bb minor, seamlessly weaving this conceptual framework

throughout the two measures. This perspective reflects his unique harmonic vision and cohesive melodic development.

Example 4.99 “Full House,” mm. 87-88

In measures 113-114 (Example 4.100), Martino uses a Dbmajor7 arpeggio over the Bb minor ninth chord, followed by Bb minor materials and chromatic embellishments over the Eb9 chord to construct the melodic line. In measure 115, he employs a B chromatic approach to resolve to the third (C), then initiates a descending Ab major scale starting from Bb, creating a fluid and harmonically rich passage.

Example 4.100 “Full House,” mm. 113-115

In measure 135 (Example 4.101), over the G minor seventh flat fifth chord, Martino begins the melodic line by stepping from F to E, incorporating rests to add space and phrasing. On the final beat, he introduces the tonic F minor triad, which carries over into the second beat of the following measure. From the second beat onward, Martino transitions to using Bb minor materials, blending harmonic and melodic elements to craft a cohesive and expressive passage.

Example 4.101 “Full House,” mm. 135-136

4.6.5 Special Techniques Analysis

In measures 169-170 (Example 4.102), Martino, drawing from F melodic minor, uses the third (Ab) and fifth (C) of Fminor9, along with the root (Bb) and third (D) of Bb, to construct a melodic line enriched with double-stops. This approach adds depth and ornamentation to the melody, showcasing Martino’s skillful use of harmonic layering to enhance his improvisational expression.

Example 4.102 “Full House,” mm. 169-170

In measures 209-210 (Example 4.103), Martino uses the notes E, F, and A, incorporating a slide (gliss) combined with the 3-against-4 technique to create a fluid and dynamic melodic line across these two measures. Notably, this technique is employed throughout the entire third chorus of the piece, showcasing one of Martino’s most iconic and widely recognized approaches.

Example 4.103 “Full House,” mm. 209-210

“Full House” remained one of Martino’s most frequently performed pieces in his later years, serving as both a tribute to Wes Montgomery and a heartfelt reflection on the passage of time. This version of “Full House” prominently features traces of Wes’s signature phrases, demonstrating Martino’s enduring admiration for his friend, even in the later stages of his career. In the final chorus of the solo, Martino employs his iconic techniques, weaving them seamlessly throughout the entire section. It feels as though he is crying out a resounding “yeah, yeah, yeah” – a powerful expression of his life’s journey, pulling the audience’s emotions to an ecstatic high before gradually

releasing the tension. As the piece resolves into a calm stillness, it leaves an impression of deep philosophical introspection, encapsulating both Martino's artistry and his profound connection to the music.

CHAPTER V

PRACTICAL APPLICATIONS

After an in-depth analysis of the improvisations in six compositions from different eras in Chapter 4, this chapter introduces a structured approach to help musicians learn Pat Martino's performance characteristics: (1) all chords converted to minor, (2) embellishment practices, (3) long phrases in Pat Martino's style, (4) special guitar techniques, and (5) comprehensive application.

5.1 All Chords Converted to Minor

Through the harmonic analysis of the improvisational solos in Chapter 4, I found that Martino tends to use melodic materials drawn from the Dorian scale and the melodic minor scale in his improvisations. Furthermore, his lines generally do not differentiate clearly between the melodic minor scale and the Dorian scale. I also discovered that in the entire improvisational solo of "Just Friends," Martino predominantly employs materials from the D Aeolian scale over the primary tonal function chord Fmajor7. Based on my interpretation of Martino's style, combined with the analysis of Pat Martino's basic chord substitution in Chapter 2 and the findings in Chapter 4, the following table summarizes Martino's substitutions from the perspectives of arpeggios and scales. This presentation is designed to facilitate readers' memorization:

Table 5.1 Minor Substitutions

Chords	Substitutions
Cmajor7(9 #11 13) or Cmajor7#5 (Tonic I major or no function)	Aminor7(Dorian Scale) Aminormajor7(A Melodic Minor Scale)
Cmajor7(9 13) (Tonic I major) Eminor7(11) (Tonic III minor)	Aminor7(A Aeolian Scale)

Cminor7 or Cminormajor7	Cminor7(C Dorian Scale) Cminormajor7(C Melodic Minor Scale)
Cminor7b5	Ebminor7(Eb Dorian Scale) Ebminormajor7(Eb Melodic Minor Scale)
C7, C9, C7sus, C13, C7#11. (Consonant Dominant)	Gminor7(G Dorian Scale) Gminormajor7(G Melodic Minor Scale)
C7#11, C7b13, C7#9, C7b9, C7b9b13. (Dissonant Dominant)	Bbminormajor7(Bb Melodic Minor Scale) Dbminormajor7(Db Melodic Minor Scale) Eminormajor7(E Melodic Minor Scale) Gminormajor7(G Melodic Minor Scale) (Multiple Substitutions)
Cdim7	F#minor7(F# Dorian Scale) F#minormajor7(F# Melodic Minor Scale)

5.2 Embellishments' Practices

Melodic embellishment techniques—such as passing tones (PT), neighbor tones (NT), indirect resolution (IR), double chromatic approach (DCHR), and escape tones (ET), etc.—are commonly used in classical music, traditional jazz, modern music, and various other musical styles. From the Melodic Construction Analysis of the improvisational solos in Chapter 4, I noticed that Martino is highly adept at using embellishments to decorate the 1–b3–5–b7 chord tones of minor7 arpeggios, allowing him to develop extended and complex bebop lines. Below, I present exercises based on two-Note Melodic Embellishments and 3-Note Melodic Embellishments to help readers become more familiar with embellishment techniques applied to minor7 chord tones and, in turn, continually expand melodic lines.

5.2.1 1 Below / 1 Diatonic Above: C minor7

In Example 5.1 (i) and Example 5.2 (ii), I decorate the chord tones of C minor7 (C–Eb–G–Bb) both from below and above. The note below each chord tone is a chromatic half-step approach, while the note above each chord tone is taken from within the C Dorian scale.

¹ 1 Below / 1 Diatonic Above: Cminor7

R b3 5 b7

Example 5.1 1 Below / 1 Diatonic Above: C minor7 (i)

¹ 1 Below / 1 Diatonic Above: Cminor7

R R b3 b3 5 5 b7 b7

Example 5.2 1 Below / 1 Diatonic Above: C minor7 (ii)

5.2.2 1 Diatonic Above / 1 Below: C minor7

In Example 5.3 (i) and Example 5.4 (ii), the chord tones of Cmin7 (C–Eb–G–Bb) are again decorated, this time from above and below. The note above each chord tone is from the C Dorian scale, while the note below is a chromatic half-step approach.

¹ 1 Diatonic Above / 1 Below: Cminor7

R b3 5 b7

Example 5.3 1 Diatonic Above / 1 Below: C minor7 (i)

¹ 1 Diatonic Above / 1 Below: Cminor7

R R b3 b3 5 5 b7 b7

Example 5.4 1 Diatonic Above / 1 Below: C minor7 (ii)

5.2.3 2 Below / 1 Above: C minor7

In Example 5.5, the chord tones of C minor7 (C–Eb–G–Bb) are decorated from both below and above. To prevent too many embellishments from distorting the original sound of the chord, the chord tone is placed on the downbeat, while the approach tones begin on the offbeat. Two consecutive chromatic tones approach from below, and one chromatic tone approaches from above.

¹ 2 Below / 1 Above: Cminor7

R b3 5 b7

Example 5.5 2 Below / 1 Above: Cminor7

5.2.4 2 Above / 1 Below: C minor7

Similarly, in Example 5.6, the chord tones of C minor7 (C–Eb–G–Bb) are decorated from both above and below. Again, to prevent too many embellishments from distorting the original sound of the chord, the chord tone is played on the downbeat, while approach tones start on the offbeat. Two consecutive chromatic tones approach from above, and one chromatic tone approaches from below.

1

2 Above / 1 Below: Cminor7

Example 5.6 2 Above / 1 Below: C minor7

5.2.5 Exercises in 12 keys

The exercise below applies the aforementioned embellishments to all 12 keys using the circle of fifths. This cyclical practice helps readers further master the application of embellishment techniques to minor7 chord tones:

1 1 Below / 1 Diatonic Above: Cminor7 Fminor7

5 Bbminor7 Ebminor7

9 Abminor7 Dbminor7

13 Gbminor7 Bminor7

17 Eminor7 Aminor7

21 Dminor7 Gminor7

Example 5.7 1 Below / 1 Diatonic Above: C minor7 in all 12 keys (i)

1 1 Below / 1 Diatonic Above: Cminor7

5 Fminor7

9 Bbminor7

13 Ebminor7

17 Abminor7

21 Dbminor7

25 Gbminor7

29 Bminor7

33 Eminor7

37 Aminor7

41 Dminor7

45 Gminor7

Example 5.8 1 Below / 1 Diatonic Above: C minor7 in all 12 keys (ii)

1 1 Diatonic Above / 1 Below: Cminor7 Fminor7

5 Bbminor7 Ebminor7

9 Abminor7 Dbminor7

13 Gbminor7 Bminor7

17 Eminor7 Aminor7

21 Dminor7 Gminor7

Example 5.9 1 Diatonic Above / 1 Below: C minor7 in all 12 keys (i)

1 1 Diatonic Above / 1 Below: Cminor7

5 Fminor7

9 Bbminor7

13 Ebminor7

17 Abminor7

21 Dbminor7

25 Gbminor7

29 Bminor7

33 Eminor7

37 Aminor7

41 Dminor7

45 Gminor7

Example 5.10 1 Diatonic Above / 1 Below: C minor7 in all 12 keys (ii)

1 2 Below /1 Above: Cminor7

5 Fminor7

9 Bbminor7

13 Ebminor7

17 Abminor7

21 Dbminor7

25 Gbminor7

29 Bminor7

33 Eminor7

37 Aminor7

41 Dminor7

45 Gminor7

Example 5.11 2 Below / 1 Above: C minor7 in all 12 keys

1 2 Above / 1 Below: Cminor7

5 Fminor7

9 Bbminor7

13 Ebminor7

17 Abminor7

21 Dbminor7

25 Gbminor7

29 Bminor7

33 Eminor7

37 Aminor7

41 Dminor7

45 Gminor7

Example 5.12 2 Above / 1 Below: C minor7 in all 12 keys

5.3 Long Phrases in Pat Martino's Style

Building on the foundational minor7 embellishment materials covered in Section 5.2, here I present four extended minor phrases in Example 5.13. The first three are derived from Pat Martino's "Impressions," while the last two are from improvisational excerpts in Pat Martino's *The Nature of Guitar* course. By practicing these phrases, musicians can better understand how Martino uses embellishment techniques to develop powerful, long linear phrases, enabling them to apply these ideas with flexibility in practical settings. Performers are encouraged to practice the following excerpts with a metronome in all twelve keys, reinforcing their mastery and adaptability in real-world improvisation.

The image displays four musical phrases, numbered 1 through 4, in 4/4 time. Each phrase begins with an Am7 chord. Phrase 1 consists of four measures of eighth-note and quarter-note patterns. Phrase 2 consists of four measures, including a triplet of eighth notes in the third measure. Phrase 3 consists of five measures, including a triplet of eighth notes in the first measure. Phrase 4 consists of four measures, featuring a triplet of eighth notes in the second measure and a half-note in the final measure.

Example 5.13 Long phrases

5.4 Special Guitar Techniques

Pat Martino is known for a wide range of guitar techniques that are highly regarded by jazz musicians. In this section, I draw on the analysis of special techniques presented in Chapter 4 and provide relevant practice examples to help performers further

internalize these guitar techniques. Performers are encouraged to practice the following excerpts with a metronome. These guitar techniques, though effective, are not applied across all twelve keys but should be practiced in various keys to enhance technical proficiency and adaptability.

Example 5.14 shows an exercise that combines the double-stop technique with blues notes over a C7 and Cmajor7 harmonic backdrop.

Example 5.14 Double-Stops Exercise

Martino often favored using the slide combined with the 3-against-4 technique throughout an entire chorus as a tool to drive emotional intensity. In Example 5.15 and Example 5.16, provide foundational exercises based on A minor materials, which can also be applied to Cmajor7 and C7 contexts. In Example 5.17, I present an exercise utilizing the C Mixolydian scale as the basis for applying the slide combined with the 3-against-4 technique. Performers are encouraged to explore this approach with other scale patterns as well. Martino frequently employed this technique in his later works, such as “Sunny” and “Full House,” to enhance the emotional progression of his performance.

Example 5.15 Slide Combined with The 3-Against-4 Exercise 1

Example 5.16 Slide Combined with The 3-Against-4 Exercise 2

Example 5.17 Slide Combined with The 3-Against-4 Exercise 3

In Example 5.18, I present a practice exercise based on the A Dorian scale, incorporating the open string and string pull-off combined with the 3-against-4 technique. This approach represents an integral aspect of Pat Martino’s playing style and stands as one of his signature techniques, contributing significantly to the unique character of his performances throughout his career.

Example 5.18 Open String and String Pull-off Combined with the 3-Against-4 Exercise 1

Martino’s economic picking technique is widely admired by guitarists across the jazz world. In Examples 5.19–5.21, I present several exercises based on playing habits from different periods of Martino’s career. These exercises are indispensable for achieving Martino’s signature sound and serve as a vital foundation for understanding his technical approach to jazz guitar.

Example 5.19 Economic Picking Exercise 1

Example 5.20 Economic Picking Exercise 2

AM7

Example 5.21 Economic Picking Exercise 3

Following his return to the stage, Martino frequently used string bending in his improvisational solos, often mimicking the enthusiastic “yeah yeah yeah” cheers of an audience and igniting the emotional energy of his performances. Example 5.22 provides a concise two-measure string bending exercise designed to help readers quickly develop proficiency in this expressive technique.

AMIN027

Example 5.22 String Bend Exercise

Martino’s stairway chromaticism technique, often paired with extended linear phrases in his later works, serves as a method to connect different fretboard positions, enhancing the fluidity of his playing. To incorporate this technique into unconscious performance, mastering its foundational application is essential. In Example 5.23, I provide a practice excerpt focused on stairway chromaticism, designed to help readers quickly grasp and apply this technique in their own playing.

DM7 STAIRWAY CHROMATICISM

Example 5.23 Stairway Chromaticism Exercise

Martino’s chromatic octave displacement technique is one of his most distinctive and recognizable. He frequently employs this technique near the conclusion of his improvisational solos or during trade 4 or trade 8 sections, creating a compelling

interplay of tension and release. In Example 5.24, I provide a foundational exercise focused on the octave displacement scale, enabling performers to quickly develop proficiency with this technique and effectively incorporate it into their playing to heighten musical dynamics.

Example 5.24 Octave Displacement Exercise

5.5 Comprehensive Application

After becoming familiar with the concepts discussed above, performers are encouraged to apply the related phrases and techniques to common jazz standards. Example 5.25 shows a one-chorus solo over the standard “Autumn Leaves,” incorporating selected materials and techniques from the previous sections alongside some of Pat Martino’s signature approaches. Each technique used is clearly annotated, offering performers a practical example of how to integrate these elements into their improvisation.

AUTUMN LEAVES

YANG HU'S SOLO
EXAMPLE

The musical score is written in 4/4 time and consists of 32 measures. It is divided into three sections: A (measures 1-16), B (measures 17-24), and C (measures 25-32). The key signature has two flats (Bb and Eb).

Section A (Measures 1-16):

- Measures 1-4: Cminor materials (Chords: Cm7, F7, Ebmaj7)
- Measures 5-8: Ebminor 12b35 (Chords: Am7(b9), D7(ALT.), Gm7)
- Measures 9-12: Cminor materials (Chords: Cm7, F7, Ebmajor7, Pivot note, Ebmaj7)
- Measures 13-16: Cminor materials (Chords: Am7(b9), D7(ALT.), Gm7, Gminor materials, Gm7)

Section B (Measures 17-24):

- Measures 17-20: Cminor materials (Chords: Am7(b9), D7(ALT.), Gm7, Gminor materials, Gm7)
- Measures 21-24: Cminor materials (Chords: Cm7, F7, Bbmaj7, Ebmaj7)

Section C (Measures 25-32):

- Measures 25-28: Gm Open String and String Pull-off Combined with the 3-Against-4 (Chords: Am7(b9), Cm, D7(ALT.), Gm7, Gb13, Fm7, E13)
- Measures 29-32: Economic Picking (Chords: Am7(b9), D7(ALT.), Gm7, Gm7)

Other annotations include "Stairway Chromaticism" in measures 5-8 and 13-16, and "Double-Stops" in measure 20.

Example 5.25 "Autumn Leaves" Exercise

This chapter has presented a structured practice methodology for applying Pat Martino's improvisational techniques in performance, with a focus on five core areas. By offering a progressive and systematic approach, this chapter gradually integrates Martino's stylistic elements into the improvisational process. This approach satisfies the objective outlined in Chapter One: to design practical exercises to help musicians apply Pat Martino's theories and techniques in their playing.

CHAPTER VI

SUMMARY

6.1 Summary of Transcription Process

The transcription process in this study draws upon Pat Martino's "second nature" learning method, which emphasizes the internalization of musical content through intensive repetition of listening, singing, and playing. Before beginning the transcription, I conducted an in-depth investigation into the historical context of the selected pieces and sought to immerse myself in the moment by performing the thematic sections alongside the original recordings. Special attention was given to articulations, attempting to mimic Martino's phrasing and emotional expressions from a first-person perspective. This preparatory step ensured a profound resonance with the works, enabling a deeper understanding of the melodic and harmonic structures through active listening and memorization.

The transcription process began with singing along to the solos to develop an initial comprehension of their melodic contours and expressive dynamics. Once a firm grasp of the solos through vocalization was achieved, the next step involved translating this understanding to the guitar and visualizing the solos on the fretboard. Repeated practice at varying speeds helped establish a natural connection between the hands and the musical content, further reflecting Martino's principle of deeply embedding musical elements into one's "second nature." Ultimately, these solos were transcribed in traditional notation, laying a solid foundation for further analysis.

6.2 Summary of Musical Analysis

This study analyses six works by Pat Martino from different periods of his career: "Just Friends," "Joyous Lake," "Turnpike," "Think Tank," "Lean Year," and "Full House." The analysis focused on the key areas of melodic construction analysis,

rhythmic analysis, harmonic analysis, and special techniques analysis, offering a comprehensive exploration of Martino's musical approach and stylistic evolution.

"Just Friends" exemplifies Martino's early style, showcasing his mastery of intervallic transformation (as displayed in example 4.1), chromatic approach (as displayed in example 4.4), pivot tones (as displayed in example 4.2), and octave displacement (as displayed in example 4.5) in melodic construction. His rhythmic ingenuity is evident through rhythmic anticipation (as displayed in example 4.9), syncopation (as displayed in example 4.12), metric displacement (as displayed in example 4.10), and rhythmic intensity (as displayed in example 4.11). Harmonically, Martino employs minor substitutions (as displayed in example 4.14) and extended tonal frameworks, blending them with techniques like enclosure and chromatic embellishment to craft lines that balance tension and resolution. This piece establishes a foundation for understanding Martino's early improvisational vocabulary and stylistic identity.

"Joyous Lake" represents a significant transition in Martino's style, integrating quartal harmony (as displayed in example 4.37) with superimposed metric modulation (as displayed in example 4.28) and advanced harmonic substitutions (as displayed in example 4.36). He enhances the piece with chromatic embellishments (as displayed in example 4.27) and motivic development (as displayed in example 4.22), adding depth and fusion-like characteristics. This composition demonstrates Martino's ability to merge traditional jazz elements with innovative approaches, highlighting his creative contributions to jazz fusion.

"Turnpike" emphasizes harmonic substitutions (as displayed in example 4.48) and chromatic techniques (as displayed in example 4.41), revealing Martino's focus on tonal continuity and thematic coherence. Through rhythmic displacement (as displayed in example 4.45) and rhythmic density (as displayed in example 4.47), he achieves a dynamic balance between tension and release, showcasing a profound understanding of musical structure. This piece reflects Martino's adeptness at combining traditional jazz techniques with experimental harmonic and melodic concepts.

"Think Tank" epitomizes Martino's exploration of the post-bop idiom, characterized by minor chord substitutions (as displayed in example 4.68) and intricate

harmonic (as displayed in example 4.66) alterations layered over traditional progressions. The work seamlessly blends Martino's daring harmonic experiments with his homage to John Coltrane, resulting in a compelling fusion of innovation and emotional depth.

"Lean Year" demonstrates Martino's expertise in motivic development (as displayed in example 4.72) and emotional storytelling (as displayed in example 4.89). Through pivot tones (as displayed in example 4.76), syncopation (as displayed in example 4.79), and rhythmic density (as displayed in example 4.80), he creates a narrative-driven improvisation that alternates between high-energy passages and lyrical expression. This composition reflects Martino's mature artistic sensibility, balancing intensity with profound musical introspection.

"Full House" serves as a heartfelt tribute to Wes Montgomery, blending Montgomery's stylistic influence with Martino's innovative techniques. The piece features creative use of the 3-against-4 technique (as displayed in example 4.103), rhythmic displacement (as displayed in example 4.96), and harmonic substitutions (as displayed in example 4.99), merging hard bop language with Martino's signature approaches. It encapsulates Martino's lifelong balance between honoring tradition and asserting his own artistic voice.

Across these six works, Pat Martino's improvisational style undergoes a remarkable evolution, transitioning from the intricate bebop foundations of "Just Friends" to the harmonic boldness of "Think Tank" and the profound expressiveness of "Full House." Each composition unveils a distinct dimension of his artistry, whether it is the melodic ingenuity demonstrated through intervallic transformations and thematic development, the rhythmic complexity exemplified by syncopation, the harmonic innovation realized through substitutions and extended tonalities, or the technical mastery displayed through his iconic techniques. Together, these works illustrate Martino as a visionary guitarist who seamlessly bridges jazz tradition with modernity, carving a legacy that continues to inspire the genre.

6.3 Summary of Practical Applications

The practical application of this study is demonstrated by the exercises inspired by Pat Martino's improvisational style. These exercises are structured around five key areas: (1) all chords converted to minor, (2) embellishments' practices, (3) long phrases in Pat Martino's style, (4) special guitar techniques, and (5) comprehensive application.

In the first section, I provide a table of minor substitutions to help readers memorize the concepts, thus reducing the need for extensive thinking in real musical environments. In the second section, I present exercises for 2-note and 3-note melodic embellishments based on the chord tones of minor seventh chords. These exercises are designed to enhance the reader's ability to develop melodic lines. In the third section, I present four long phrases of minor seventh chords from Martino's works and live improvisations to reinforce the embellishment techniques learned in the second section, providing a deeper understanding of how Martino applies these techniques in practice.

In the fourth section, I introduce guitar-specific technical exercises addressing the core elements of Martino's style. By breaking down these technical elements into manageable parts, musicians can better understand, integrate, and incorporate these techniques into their daily practice. Finally, comprehensive exercises play an indispensable role in bridging theory and practice. Through analytical exploration, musicians can identify appropriate techniques or phrases for specific harmonic contexts. A focused application of these concepts on standard repertoire, such as "Autumn Leaves," serves to solidify their understanding of harmonic flexibility while enabling them to naturally embody Martino's improvisational characteristics.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

TRANSCRIPTION OF “JUST FRIENDS”

JUST FRIENDS

PAT MARTINO'S SOLO
ALBUM: EL HOMBRE (1967)
TRANSCRIBED BY YANG HU

39 Fmaj7 40

41 **A** FIRST CHORUS Bbmaj7 Bbm7 Eb7

45 Fmaj7 Abm7 Db7

49 **B** Gm7 C7 Em7(b9) A7 Dm7

55 G7 Gm7 C7 F7

57 **A** Bbmaj7 Bbm7 Eb7

61 Fmaj7 Abm7 Db7

65 **C** Gm7 C7 Em7(b9) A7 Dm7

69 G7 Gm7 C7 Fmaj7 Cm7 F7

75 **A** SECOND CHORUS Bbmaj7 Bbm7 Eb7

77 Fmaj7 Abm7 Db7

2

81 **B** Gm7 C7 Em7(b9) A7 Dm7

85 G7 Gm7 C7 F7

89 **A** Bbmaj7 Bbm7 Eb7

93 Fmaj7 Abm7 Db7

97 **C** Gm7 C7 Em7(b9) A7 Dm7

101 G7 Gm7 C7 Fmaj7 Cm7 F7

THIRD CHORUS

105 **A** Bbmaj7 Bbm7 Eb7

109 Fmaj7 Abm7 Db7

113 **B** Gm7 C7 Em7(b9) A7 Dm7

117 G7 Gm7 C7 F7

121 **A** Bbmaj7 Bbm7 Eb7

125 Fmaj7 Abm7 Db7

Detailed description: This is a guitar score for a piece in E-flat major. It consists of 12 measures of music, organized into three systems of four measures each. The key signature has three flats (B-flat, E-flat, A-flat). The score includes several section markers: 'B' at measure 81, 'A' at measure 89, and 'C' at measure 97. A 'THIRD CHORUS' label is placed below measure 101. The chords used are: Gm7, C7, Em7(b9), A7, Dm7, G7, Bbmaj7, Bbm7, Eb7, Fmaj7, Abm7, and Db7. The melody is written in a single staff with a treble clef and a key signature of three flats. Measure numbers 81, 85, 89, 93, 97, 101, 105, 109, 113, 117, 121, and 125 are indicated at the start of their respective lines.

129 **C** Gm⁷ C⁷ Em⁷(b⁹) A⁷ Dm⁷ 3

135 G⁷ Gm⁷ C⁷ Fmaj⁷ Cm⁷ F⁷

Detailed description: The musical score consists of two staves. The first staff begins at measure 129 with a common time signature 'C' in a box. The key signature has one sharp (F#). The melody starts with a quarter note G4, followed by eighth notes A4, B4, C5, B4, A4, G4. Chords Gm7, C7, Em7(b9), A7, and Dm7 are indicated above the staff. The second staff begins at measure 135 with a quarter note G4, followed by quarter notes F#4, E4, D4, C4. Chords G7, Gm7, C7, Fmaj7, Cm7, and F7 are indicated above the staff. The piece concludes with a double bar line.

APPENDIX B

TRANSCRIPTION OF "JOYOUS LAKE"

JOYOUS LAKE

PAT MARTINO'S SOLO
ALBUM: JOYOUS LAKE
TRANSCRIBED BY YANG HU

63 **A** A7

66

70

73

76

79

82

85 A7($\sharp 3$) **B** Dm7

88 C7 Am¹³ A7($\sharp 3$)

91 Dm7 C7(SUS4)

2

93 $Bm7(\flat 5)$ $E7(\flat 9)$ **A** $Am7$

96

98

100

102 $Dm7$ **B**

104 $C7(\flat 9 \flat 4)$ $Am7$ ³

107 $Dm7$ C^{13} $Bm7(\flat 5)$

110 $E7(\flat 9)$ **A** $Am7$

113

115 ³

117 **B** Dm^9

120 $C7(\flat 13)$ A^7

Musical score for guitar, measures 123-132. The score is written in treble clef with a key signature of two sharps (F# and C#). Measure 123 features a triplet of eighth notes with a Dm^{11} chord above. Measure 124 continues the triplet with a C^7 chord. Measure 125 concludes the triplet with a $Bm^7(\flat 9)$ chord. Measure 126 begins with a $E^7(\flat 9)$ chord and a triplet of eighth notes, followed by a boxed A chord and an A^7 chord. Measure 129 contains a series of chords: $F\#m^7(\flat 9)$, $C\#m^7(\flat 9)$, $F\#m^7(\flat 9)$, $C\#m^7(\flat 9)$, $F\#m^7(\flat 9)$, and $C\#m^7(\flat 9)$. Measure 132 concludes with a final chord, $F\#m^7(\flat 9)$.

APPENDIX C

TRANSCRIPTION OF “TURNPIKE”

TURNPIKE

PAT MARTINO'S SOLO
 ALBUM: LIVE AT THE KNITTING FACTORY, NYC
 TRANSCRIBED BY YANG HU

64 $D7(\sharp 9)$

65 **A** $E\flat maj7/G$

69 $A\flat 9$

75 $G\flat maj7/B\flat$ $A7$ $D7(\sharp 9)$

77 F/G $D7(\sharp 9)$

81 **A** $E\flat maj7/G$

85

89 $G\flat maj7/B\flat$ $A7(\sharp 9)$ $D7(\sharp 9)$

95 F/G

97 $Dm7(\flat 9)/E$

2

101 $Dm7(b9)/E$

105

109

115 $Ebmaj7/G$ **C**

117 $A\flat9$

121 $Gbmaj7/B\flat$ $A7$ $D7(\sharp9)$

125 F/G $D7(\sharp9)$

APPENDIX D

TRANSCRIPTION OF "THINK TANK"

PAT MARTINO'S SOLO
ALBUM: THINK TANK
TRANSCRIBED BY YANG HU

THINK TANK

116 Am7(add11)

FIRST CHORUS

117 A Am7(add11)

122 B⁷ALT.

126 E⁷ALT.

129 Am7(add11)

SECOND CHORUS

135 A Am7(add11)

136

139 B⁷ALT.

142 E⁷ALT.

144 Am7(add11)

2

THIRD CHORUS

147 A $Am7(add1)$

150

152

154

156 $B^7_{ALT.}$

159 $E^7_{ALT.}$ $Am7(add1)$

162

165 A FOURTH CHORUS $Am7(add1)$

168

171 $B^7_{ALT.}$

174 $E^7_{ALT.}$

177 $Am7(add1)$

FIFTH CHORUS

180 **A** Am7(add11) 3

184 10 3

186 3 7 7 7 7 7

189 B7(alt.) E7(alt.) 7 7 7 3

192 Am7(add11) 3 3 3

194 3 3 3 3 3 3 3 3

INTERLUDE

197 Am7(add11) 3 3 3 3 3 3

201 3 3 3 3 3 3

205 6 6 6 3 E7(alt.)

APPENDIX E

TRANSCRIPTION OF “LEAN YEARS”

LEAN YEARS

PAT MARTINO'S SOLO
 ALBUM: UNDENIABLE: LIVE AT BLUES ALLEY
 TRANSCRIBED BY YANG HU

FIRST CHORUS

65 **A** Dm⁹ Dm⁹ Dm⁹ Dm⁹

69 Dm⁹ Dm⁹ Dm⁹ Dm⁹

75 Cm⁹ F⁹ Bbmaj⁹ A7(b13)

77 Dm⁹ Dm⁹ Dm⁹ Dm⁹

81 **A** Dm⁹ Dm⁹ Dm⁹ Dm⁹

85 Dm⁹ Dm⁹ Dm⁹ Dm⁹

89 Cm⁹ F⁹ Bbmaj⁹ A7(b13)

95 Dm⁹ Dm⁹ Dm⁹ Dm⁹

97 **B** Ebm⁹ Ebm⁹ Ebm⁹ Ebm⁹

101 Ebm⁹ Ebm⁹ Ebm⁹ Ebm⁹

2

105 $D\flat m^9$ $D\flat m^9$ $D\flat m^9$ $D\flat m^9$

109 $D\flat m^9$ $D\flat m^9$ $D\flat m^9$ $D\flat m^9$

115 Dm^9 Dm^9 Dm^9 Dm^9

117 Dm^9 Dm^9 Dm^9 Dm^9

121 Cm^9 F^9 $B\flat maj^9$ $A7(\flat 13)$

125 Dm^9 Dm^9 Dm^9 Dm^9

129 **A** SECOND CHORUS Dm^9 Dm^9 Dm^9 Dm^9

135 Dm^9 Dm^9 Dm^9 Dm^9

137 Cm^9 F^9 $B\flat maj^9$ $A7(\flat 13)$

141 Dm^9 Dm^9 Dm^9 Dm^9

145 **A** Dm^9 Dm^9 Dm^9 Dm^9

149 Dm^9 Dm^9 Dm^9 Dm^9

155 Cm⁹ F⁹ Bbmaj⁹ A7(b13) 3

157 Dm⁹ Dm⁹ Dm⁹ Dm⁹ 3

161 8 Ebm⁹ Ebm⁹ Ebm⁹ Ebm⁹

165 Ebm⁹ Ebm⁹ Ebm⁹ Ebm⁹

169 Dbm⁹ Dbm⁹ Dbm⁹ Dbm⁹

173 Dbm⁹ Dbm⁹ Dbm⁹ Dbm⁹

177 C Dm⁹ Dm⁹ Dm⁹ Dm⁹ 3 3

181 Dm⁹ Dm⁹ Dm⁹ Dm⁹

185 Cm⁹ F⁹ Bbmaj⁹ A7(b13)

189 Dm⁹ Dm⁹ Dm⁹ Dm⁹

APPENDIX F

TRANSCRIPTION OF “FULL HOUSE”

FULL HOUSE

PAT MARTINO'S SOLO

ALBUM: PAT MARTINO TRIO, BIELSKA ZADYMKA JAZZOWA

TRANSCRIBED BY YANG HU

FIRST CHORUS

The musical score is written in treble clef with a key signature of three flats (B-flat major/C minor) and a 3/4 time signature. It consists of nine staves of music, each with a measure number on the left. Chords are indicated above the notes. Section markers 'A' and 'B' are placed in boxes above the first and eighth staves, respectively.

Staff 81: Chords: A, Fm⁹, Bb¹³, Fm⁹, Bb¹³. Section marker: A.

Staff 85: Chords: Fm⁹, Bb¹³, Gm7(b9), C7(b9).

Staff 89: Chords: Fm⁹, Bb¹³, Fm⁹, Bb¹³.

Staff 95: Chords: Fm⁹, Bb¹³, G⁷, C7(b13), Fm⁹.

Staff 97: Chords: A, Fm⁹, Bb¹³, Fm⁹, Bb¹³. Section marker: A.

Staff 101: Chords: Fm⁹, Bb¹³, Gm7(b9), C7(b9).

Staff 105: Chords: Fm⁹, Bb¹³, Fm⁹, Bb¹³.

Staff 109: Chords: Fm⁹, Bb¹³, G⁷, C7(b13), Fm⁹.

Staff 115: Chords: Bbm⁹, Eb⁹, Abmaj7, Db⁹. Section marker: B.

Staff 117: Chords: F#maj7, Bb⁹, Gm7(b9), C7(b9).

2

121 $Bb m^9$ $E b^9$ $A b m a j 7$ $D b^9$

125 $F \# m a j 7$ $B b^9$ $G m 7 (b^9)$ $C 7 (b^9)$

129 **A** $F m^9$ $B b^{13}$ $F m^9$ $B b^{13}$

135 $F m^9$ $B b^{13}$ $G m 7 (b^9)$ $C 7 (b^9)$

137 $F m^9$ $B b^{13}$ $F m^9$ $B b^{13}$

141 $F m^9$ $B b^{13}$ $G 7$ $C 7 (b^{13})$ $F m^9$

SECOND CHORUS **A** $F m^9$ $B b^{13}$ $F m^9$ $B b^{13}$

145

149 $F m^9$ $B b^{13}$ $G m 7 (b^9)$ $C 7 (b^9)$

155 $F m^9$ $B b^{13}$ $F m^9$ $B b^{13}$

157 $F m^9$ $B b^{13}$ $G 7$ $C 7 (b^{13})$ $F m^9$

161 **A** $F m^9$ $B b^{13}$ $F m^9$ $B b^{13}$

165 $F m^9$ $B b^{13}$ $G m 7 (b^9)$ $C 7 (b^9)$

3

169 Fm^9 Bb^{13} Fm^9 Bb^{13}

175 Fm^9 Bb^{13} G^7 $C^7(b^9)$ Fm^9

177 **B** Bbm^9 Eb^9 $Abmaj7$ D^b9

181 $F\#maj7$ Bb^9 $Gm^7(b^9)$ $C^7(b^9)$

185 Bbm^9 Eb^9 $Abmaj7$ D^b9

189 $F\#maj7$ Bb^9 $Gm^7(b^9)$ $C^7(b^9)$

195 **A** Fm^9 Bb^{13} Fm^9 Bb^{13}

197 Fm^9 Bb^{13} $Gm^7(b^9)$ $C^7(b^9)$

201 Fm^9 Bb^{13} Fm^9 Bb^{13}

205 Fm^9 Bb^{13} G^7 $C^7(b^9)$ Fm^9

THIRD CHORUS **A** 209 Fm^9 Bb^{13} Fm^9 Bb^{13}

215 Fm^9 Bb^{13} $Gm^7(b^9)$ $C^7(b^9)$

BIOGRAPHY

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